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Privacy of Vehicular Time Series Data

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Abstract

Data is the new oil for the car industry. Cars generate data about how and where they are used and who is behind the wheel which gives rise to a novel way of profiling individuals in order to provide personalized, value-added services. Information about how people are using their vehicles enables a wide number of applications, e.g., personalized insurances or advertisements, traffic maps or urban planning, where the benign side is aiming to improve quality of life. Alas, the availability of drivers' vehicle data can potentially reveal sensitive information about them such as home and work places, lifestyles, political or religious inclinations or even sexual orientation. In this dissertation we address both anonymization and de-anonymization of vehicular data. In our first scenario, we presume an attacker that is capable of acquiring in-vehicle network logs from the targeted driver and also can make test drives with an arbitrarily chosen vehicle. The goal of the attacker is to identify any individual among the people present in the dataset, i.e. singling out. Since the format of in-vehicular network logs are proprietary the attacker must find a way to utilize the data even without the knowledge of the logging protocol. In the second scenario we demonstrate a mitigation against a weaker adversary, that is only possesses location data of vehicles (e.g., GPS coordinates). We present a novel technique for privately releasing a composite generative model and whole high-dimensional location datasets with detailed time information and the guarantee of Differential Privacy. My work does not only raise the flag to car drivers, but also to companies collecting vehicular logs; the re-identification (and/or profiling) of drivers so effortlessly means that vehicular logs indeed constitute personal data and, as such, are subject to the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and mitigation often falls short of utility expectations. Overall, the techniques presented in this thesis can be used by data controllers and processors to both mitigate against attacks or to assess their level of privacy protection of their already existing anonymization methods.

Kivonat

Az autóipar legújabb olaja nem más, mint maga az adat. Járműveink adatokat generálnak arról, hogy hogyan és hol használjuk őket, és hogy éppen ki ül a volán mögött. Ez új lehetőséget nyújt a profilalkotásra, amivel az autóipar személyre szabott, értéknövelt szolgáltatásokat nyújthat a felhasználók számára. Az információk, amelyek megmutatják, hogy az emberek hogyan használják járműveiket, számos alkalmazást tesz lehetővé, többek közt személyre szabott biztosításokat vagy hirdetések, közlekedési térképeket vagy város-tervezést, ahol a jóindulatú oldal az életminőség javítását célozza. Sajnos a járművezetők adatainak elérhetősége érzékeny információkat fedhet fel a vezetőkről, például otthonukról és munkahelyükről, életmódjukról, politikai vagy vallási meggyőződésükről, vagy akár szexuális irányultságukról. Ebben a disszertációban a járműadatok anonimizálásával és újraazonosításával egyaránt foglalkozom. Első megközelítésemben feltételezem, hogy egy támadó képes a megcélzott sofőrtől származó jármű-hálózati naplókhoz hozzáférni, továbbá tesztvezetések is végezhet egy tetszőlegesen kiválasztott járművel. A támadó célja bármely személy azonosítása az adatkészletben jelenlévő személyek közül, azaz annak kiemelése ("singling-out"). Mivel a járműben lévő hálózati naplók formátuma védett, a támadónak meg kell találnia a módját, hogy a naplózási protokoll ismerete nélkül is hasznosítsa az adatokat. A második megközelítésemben egy gyengébb támadóval szembeni védekezést mutatunk be. Itt a támadó csak a járművek helyadataival (pl. GPS-koordinátáival) rendelkezik. A bemutatott új technika egy összetett generatív modell, amely teljes, nagy dimenziós helyadatkészletek privát kiadására képes részletes időinformációkkal kiegészítve, valamint a differenciális adatvédelem garanciájával. Munkám nemcsak az autóvezetőket, hanem a járműnaplók gyűjtő cégeket is célozza; a járművezetők újraazonosítása (és/vagy profilozása) különösebb erőfeszítés nélkül is lehetséges. Ez azt jelenti, hogy a járműnaplók valóban személyes adatoknak minősülnek, és mint ilyenek, az általános európai adatvédelmi rendelet (GDPR) hatálya alá tartoznak, az adatok védelmének minősége viszont elmarad az elvártaktól. Összességében elmondható, hogy a dolgozatban bemutatott technikákat az adatkezelők és -feldolgozók egyaránt használhatják a támadások mérséklésére vagy a már meglévő anonimizálási módszereik adatvédelmi teljesítményének felmérésére.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

We move around all the time. Almost every day we start the engine in our car, hop on a bus, flag down a taxi, ride the bicycle or we simply just walk. In fact, we move around so much that we often forget about our footprint. Not all of these footprints vanish into thin air or fade into the crowd: many stick, creating a unique pattern. In fact, we like to move around so much that we want to make it comfortable, and comfort can be aided and enhanced by data: our data. We can use the data produced by our vehicles and build better cars, better services, more comfort. We can use the data that locates us to build livable cities, with better traffic, smarter service distribution or even less pollution.

This digital footprint is growing at an extraordinary scale. We use numerous devices and online services creating massive amount of data 24/7. Some of these data are personal, concerning either an identified or an identifiable natural person; thus, they fall under the scope of the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [31]. In fact, to determine whether a natural person is identifiable based on given data, one should take account of all means reasonably likely to be used (by the data controller or an adversary) to identify the natural person. There are many and depend on how and where the data were collected.

In the automotive industry, the digitalization and data generation are particularly booming. From a set of mechanical and electrical components, cars have evolved into smart cyber-physical systems. Whereas this evolution has enabled automakers to implement advanced monitoring, safety and entertainment functionalities, it does not only raise the question whether this data falls under GDPR regulations; it has also opened up novel attack surfaces for malicious hackers and data collection opportunities for Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), i.e., car makers and third parties. A naively anonymized dataset does not contain names, home addresses, phone numbers or other obvious identifiers. Yet, if an individual's driving patterns are unique enough, outside information can be used to link the data back to them. All together, the prevalence of

vehicle datasets, the uniqueness of human traces and the information that can be inferred from them highlight the importance of understanding the privacy bounds of vehicle data practices. Decades of research shows that large datasets can often be de-anonymized and used to reveal sensitive information about individual people (e.g., [33]). Furthermore, existing anonymization solutions often come with low utility, which renders them inapplicable in real-life scenarios.

In this dissertation we examine the privacy implications of releasing data captured from the network that connects Electronic Control Units (ECUs) inside a vehicle. Furthermore, we investigate the anonymization of location information (e.g., GPS coordinates) of a moving vehicle.

Considering in-vehicle data, the most established vehicular network standard is called Controller Area Network (CAN) [71]. CAN is already a critical technology worldwide making automotive data access a commodity. One or more CAN buses carry all important driving related information inside a car. OEMs collect and analyze CAN data for maintenance purposes; however, CAN data might reveal other, more personal traits, such as the driving behavior of natural persons (e.g., [27]). Such information could be invaluable to third party service providers such as insurance companies, fleet management services and other location-based businesses (not to mention malicious entities), hence there exist economic incentives for them to collect or buy them¹. Unfortunately, sharing in-vehicle network data raises serious privacy concerns. Although drivers are expected to opt-in to such data sharing², it is still unclear what exact personal information they would transfer then to third parties. For example, can a skilled data analyst infer the driver's identity using *only* in-vehicle network data? Despite the inherently noisy nature of this fine-grained measurement data, the feasibility of driver identification has been demonstrated in several prior works [28, 44, 56, 78]. In particular, it is well-known that drivers can be re-identified in constrained environments if they follow the same route with the same car and sensor readings are available from the captured network logs [28]. However, when following different routes, unique driving patterns are more difficult to extract due to the variable traffic conditions. Also, it is much more plausible that an adversary is able to collect CAN logs from arbitrary routes. Moreover, car manufacturers do not disclose the exact format of CAN messages and therefore the precise signal location within these messages, in order to protect their intellectual property against competitors, as well as the security of drivers against malicious car hacking. But is this approach of security/privacy by obscurity effective? In Chapter 2 we show that not revealing the exact signal location

¹<https://www.forbes.com/sites/petercohan/2017/09/29/this-startup-is-helping-daimler-and-bmw-compete-with-google-for-10-trillion-market/>

²www.wsj.com/articles/what-your-car-knows-about-you-1534564861

in CAN logs is not sufficient to provide any privacy guarantee in practice. Car companies should devise more principled approaches to hide signals, and/or to anonymize their CAN logs so that drivers cannot be re-identified. In this chapter we presume a fairly weak adversary for this scenario, who is capable of acquiring the in-vehicle network logs of the targeted individual and also can make test drives in an arbitrarily chosen vehicle. The goal of the attacker is to identify any individual among the people present in the dataset, i.e. singling out. In-vehicular logging protocols are proprietary, which means that the attacker must find a way to utilize the data even without the knowledge of the protocol. We show two ways that an attacker can easily circumvent this problem, first, we show that reverse engineering is not difficult, but takes some time and effort. To overcome this hardship, we provide a second solution, where we show that this reverse engineering is not even necessary, an adversary can solve the re-identification problem even without the knowledge of the protocol. Therefore, not releasing the protocol details is not sufficient to provide any sort of meaningful anonymity guarantee.

Next, in Chapter 3 we presume a different attacker, who has access to a database of location coordinates of different vehicular trajectories (e.g., taxi drives, personal car drives or even bicycle ride trajectories). The goal of the attacker remains the same i.e., singling out a targeted individual. It is far from difficult to gain access to such datasets. The location data industry is booming, having created an already \$12 billion market, and it is steadily expanding with companies that harvest, sell, or trade in location data. Many of these firms claim that privacy is of utmost importance in their businesses and that they never sell personal data.³ However, collecting and mining location data come inherently with their own strong privacy and other ethical concerns [9]. Several studies have shown that pseudonymization and quasi-standard de-identification are not sufficient to prevent users from being re-identified in location datasets [19] [77]. This not only infringe upon the rights of drivers, but also significantly hinders location data sharing and use by researchers, developers and humanitarian workers alike⁴.

Although a plethora of different anonymization techniques have been proposed for location data ([33]), they all suffer from either weak utility or weak privacy guarantees, or they do not scale to large datasets. Indeed, location data is inherently high-dimensional and often sparse, which makes an individual's location trace unique even in very large populations⁵. This has a detrimental effect on privacy, and also on utility due to the curse of dimensionality. Note that aggregation per se does not necessarily prevent such

³<https://themarkup.org/privacy/2021/09/30/theres-a-multibillion-dollar-market-for-your-phones-location-data>

⁴<https://www.economist.com/leaders/2014/10/23/call-for-help>

⁵Four data points—approximate places and times where an individual was present—have been demonstrated to be enough to uniquely re-identify 95% of the users in a dataset of 1.5 million users [19]

re-identification in practice [75, 62]. The brittleness of privacy guarantees ignited research towards location anonymization with provable privacy guarantees. So far, only a handful of prior works [17, 47, 42, 11] have addressed the off-line anonymization of complete location trajectories with formal privacy guarantees. Most of these approaches use some form of differential privacy [25], which has become the *de facto* privacy model in recent years [29, 2, 69]. However, most of previous techniques suffer from the inherent sparseness and high dimensionality of location trajectories which render them impractical, resulting in unrealistic traces and unscalable methods. Furthermore, time information of location visits is usually dropped, or its resolution is drastically reduced. In this work we present a novel technique for privately releasing a composite generative model and whole high-dimensional location datasets with detailed time information. To generate high-fidelity synthetic data, we leverage several peculiarities of vehicular mobility such as its language-like characteristics (“you should know a *location* by the company it keeps”) or how humans plan their trips from one point to the other. We model the generator distribution of the dataset by first constructing a variational autoencoder to generate the source and destination locations, and the corresponding timing of trajectories. Next, we compute transition probabilities between locations with a feed forward network, and build a transition graph from the output of this model, which approximates the distribution of all paths between the source and destination (at a given time). Finally, a path is sampled from this distribution with a Markov Chain Monte Carlo method. The generated synthetic dataset is highly realistic, scalable, provides good utility and, nonetheless, provably private. We evaluate our model against two state-of-the-art methods and three real-life datasets demonstrating the benefits of our approach.

1.1 Research objectives

The objective of my research is threefold.

1. We investigate experimentally the potential to reverse-engineer (identify and extract) vehicle sensor signals from raw CAN bus data for the sake of inferring personal driving behavior and re-identifying drivers. (Chapter 2.2)
2. We demonstrate the feasibility of driver re-identification even when drivers follow different routes and the exact signals (such as velocity, acceleration, RPM, etc.) cannot be extracted directly from the captured CAN log. The technique is scalable and is able to classify a large set of time series even if many of the individual time series are significantly noisy and, hence, lack sufficient predictive power individually. (Chapter 2.3)

3. We propose a novel generative model, DP-Loc to generate realistic location trajectories with time information. This composite generative model can be trained with differentially private gradient descent on sensitive location data, and, therefore, can be used to synthesize the training data with formally proven privacy guarantees. Such synthetic training data can be shared for any purposes without violating individuals' privacy. (Chapter 3)

Chapter 2

In-vehicular Data Privacy

2.1 Background

Here we give a brief overview on the in-vehicle dataset that we investigate throughout this chapter.

2.1.1 CAN: Controller Area Network

Almost all vehicles in use nowadays are equipped with various on-board Electrical Control Units (ECUs), sensors and actuators measuring and controlling the vehicle's speed, acceleration, braking, fuel consumption, battery status, or tire pressure level, among others. Sensors attached to their respective ECUs, whose number ranges from 5 to a hundred per vehicle, continuously generate a vast amount of real-time data. In order to implement complex control tasks for traffic safety or passenger infotainment, these data are then transferred among ECUs and other nodes over the in-vehicle network, most commonly following the Controller Area Network (CAN) bus standard [68].

The first CAN bus protocol was developed in 1986, and it was adopted as an international standard in 1993 (ISO 11898). A recent car can have anywhere from 5 up to 100 ECUs, which are served by several CANs. Our point of focus is the CAN serving the drive-train.

CAN is an overloaded term [68]. Originally, CAN refers to the ISO standard 11898-1 specifying the physical and data link layers of the CAN protocol stack. Second, another meaning is connected to FMS-CAN (Fleet Management System CAN), originally initiated by major truck manufacturers, defined in the SAE standard family J1939; FMS-CAN gives a full-stack specification including recommendations on higher protocol layers. Third, CAN refers to the multitude of proprietary CAN protocols which are make and model specific. This results in different message IDs, signal transformation parameters

and encoding. These protocols are usually based on the standardized lower layers, but their higher layers are kept confidential by OEMs. The overwhelming majority of cars use one or more proprietary CAN protocols. Generally, sensor signals in CAN variants have a sampling frequency in the order of 10 ms, i.e., an ECU packs the measured signal samples into a CAN message and broadcasts that on the CAN bus every 10 ms.

On the other hand, using the standard on-board diagnostics (OBD, OBD-II) is a popular way of getting data out of the car. Originally developed for maintenance and technical inspection purposes and included in every new car since 1996, OBD is also used for telematics applications. Adding to the confusion regarding CAN, OBD has five minor variations including one which is based on the CAN physical layer. Sensor signals carried by OBD have a sampling frequency in the order of 1s. In certain vehicle makes and models, one or more CANs are also connected to the OBD-II diagnostic port. In such cars, also utilizing OBD over the CAN physical layer, it is possible to extract fine-grained CAN data via an OBD-II logger device [68]. Indeed, collecting in-vehicle network logs is not a privilege of car companies any more. For example, insurance companies sell a complete kit which consists of a smartphone application as well as an OBD-II adapter. This adapter is then voluntarily installed by the driver and wirelessly connected to the driver's smartphone through Bluetooth¹.

However, owing to the confidential message format and semantics, extracting a sensor signal from the captured CAN messages is not straightforward. Table 2.1 shows a simplified picture of a CAN message with a 11-bit identifier, which is the usual format for everyday cars; trucks and buses usually use the extended 29-bit version. This example shows an already stripped message, i.e., we do not discuss end of frame or check bits. We will show in chapter 2.2 that the Data field can be broken to sensor signals which are then transformed and/or converted to a human-readable format in order to enable further analysis. For example, the position of the brake pedal may be carried by the fourth byte of the message with ID 0x02c4 in Table 2.1. Therefore, extracting the fourth byte of every consecutive instance of this message type (ordered by their timestamp) one can reconstruct the braking signal (i.e., position of the brake pedal over time, which is shown in green in Table 2.1). *Importantly, the message ID, offset and length of a signal are not standardised and kept confidential by OEMs.* Consequently, extracting a signal from recorded CAN messages would require (partly) reverse-engineering the specific CAN protocol which may be illegal under practical circumstances [12].

¹Other malicious parties may have access to the driver's device by installing a malicious application which then may gain access to the adapter.

Timestamp	CAN-ID	Req	Len	Data
1481492683.285052	0x0208	000	0x8	0x00 0x00 0x32 0x00 0x0e 0x32 0xfe 0x3c
1481492674.736055	0x02c4	000	0x8	0x82 0xc8 0x00 0x0f 0x03 0x00 0x92 0x3c
1481492674.736055	0x02c4	000	0x8	0x82 0xc9 0x00 0x0f 0x00 0x00 0x92 0x4c
1481492674.736055	0x02c4	000	0x8	0x82 0xcc 0x00 0x0f 0x08 0x00 0x92 0x5a
1497323915.123844	0x018e	000	0x8	0x03 0x03 0x00 0x00 0x00 0x00 0x07 0x3f
1497323915.112910	0x00f1	000	0x6	0x28 0x00 0x00 0x40 0x00 0x00
1481492674.736055	0x02c4	000	0x8	0x82 0xd2 0x00 0x0f 0x0c 0x00 0x92 0x5d
1481492674.736055	0x02c4	000	0x8	0x82 0xa1 0x00 0x0f 0xa1 0x00 0x92 0x4d

Table 2.1: Example of CAN messages and the extracted time series. The red, green, and blue time series are obtained by extracting the 1st, 4th and 7th byte of every time-ordered CAN message with ID 0x02c4, respectively.

Components of a CAN bus message.

- Timestamp: Unix timestamp of the message
- CAN-ID: contains the message identifier - lower values have higher priority (e.g., wheel angle, speed, ...)
- Remote Transmission Request: allows ECUs to request messages from other ECUs
- Length: length of the Data field in bytes (0 to 8 bytes)
- Data: contains the actual data values in hexadecimal format. The Data field needs to be broken to sensor signals, transformed and/or converted to a human-readable format in order to enable further analysis.

Throughout this dissertation, we focus on the three practically relevant fields: CAN-ID, Length and Data. Note, that the timestamp is not sent on the CAN bus, this was added by our logging device for the sake of future analysis.

2.1.2 Data collection

As CAN data logs are not widely available, we conducted a measurement campaign. For data collection in particular we connected a logging device to the OBD-II port and logged all observed messages from various ECUs. Such a device acts as a node on the CAN bus and is able to read and store all broadcasted messages. Our team developed both the logging device (based on a Raspberry PI 3) and the logging software (in C). Note that it is common that the OBD2 connector is found under the steering wheel. Also note that not all car makes and models connect the CAN serving the drive-train ECUs (or any CAN) to the OBD-II port (e.g., Volkswagen, BMW, etc.); in this case we could not log any meaningful data.

We have gathered meaningful data from 8 different cars and a total number of 33 drivers. We did not put any restriction on the demographics of the different drivers or the route taken. In each case we asked the driver to drive for a period of 30-60 minutes, while our device logged data from every route the drivers took. Drivers were free to choose their way, but still conforming to three practical requirements: (1) record at least 2 hours of driving in total, (2) do not record data when driving up and down on hills or mountains, (3) do not record data in extremely heavy traffic (short runs and idling). Free driving was recorded for all 33 drivers with an Opel Astra 2018: 13 people were between the age of 20-30, 12 between 30-40, and 8 above 40; there were 5 women and 28 men; 11 with less experience (less than 7000 km per year on average or novice driver), 9 with average experience (8-14000 km per year), and 13 with above average experience (more than 14000 km per year).

We gathered data from the following cars: Citroen C4 2005 (22 message IDs), Toyota Corolla 2008 (36 IDs), Toyota Aygo 2014 (48 IDs), Renault Megane 2007 (20 IDs), Opel Astra 2018 (72 IDs), Opel Astra 2006 (18 IDs), Nissan X-trail 2008 (automatic, 34 IDs) and Nissan Qashqai 2015 (60 IDs). We would like to emphasize that the two Opel Astras use completely different proprietary CAN versions (even the only 2 common IDs correspond to completely different Data). We also recorded the GPS coordinates via an Android smartphone during at least one logged drive per car. Most routes were driven inside or close to Budapest; approximately 15-20% was recorded on a motorway.

Besides free driving courses we have also recorded drives from a predefined path as well. For this purpose we have used the Opel Astra, 2006 and the Toyota Yaris, 2006. 6 people (5 men and 1 women) drove via a predefined route approximately at the same time of the day, that is early afternoon to avoid too high and too low traffic. The route starts at the university and goes to a local mall, turns around and comes back on almost the same way. This path includes a downtown area and a motorway part as well. One

Figure 2.1: A driver’s fixed route illustrated by its GPS signal.

route took approximately 30-40 minutes.

In concise we have two databases: a large database of logs from different vehicles with very limited requirements but the data is very diverse, and a smaller database with restricted conditions. Both of them contains the GPS signals for each route.

The data were collected with the users’ explicit consent after informing them about the purpose of the study. Exact identity of drivers was not recorded except for their personal attributes described above. Traces of different drivers were linked together using random identifiers. Additional statistics can be seen in Table 2.2

Table 2.2: Dataset summary.

<i>Attribute</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>Population</i>
Gender	Male	28
	Female	5
Age	[20-25]	11
	[25-30]	8
	[30-40]	7
	[40-70]	7
Experience	Low	12
	Average	11
	High	10

2.2 Extracting vehicle sensor signals from CAN logs for driver re-identification

Cars generate data about how they are used and who’s behind the wheel which gives rise to a novel way of profiling individuals. Several prior works have successfully demonstrated the feasibility of driver re-identification using the in-vehicle network data captured on the vehicle’s CAN bus [27]. Using machine learning techniques, authors re-identified drivers from a fixed set of experiment participants, thus implementing singling out, which makes this a privacy threat. Moreover, all of them used signals (e.g., velocity, brake pedal or accelerator position) that have already been extracted (and identified) from the CAN log which is itself not a straightforward process. Indeed, car manufacturers intentionally do not reveal the exact signal location within CAN logs. This means, that the adversary has to know the higher layer protocols of CAN in order to extract meaningful sensor readings. Since such message and message flow specifications (above the data link layer) are usually proprietary and closely guarded industrial secrets, such adversarial background knowledge might not be reasonable. In this case, the research question changes: is it possible for an adversary to re-identify drivers based on raw CAN data without the knowledge of protocols above the data link layer?

In this chapter, we show that signals can be efficiently extracted from CAN logs using machine learning techniques. Note, that signal positions, lengths and coding are not just proprietary, but vary among makes, models, model years and even geographical area. It is a highly unlikely scenario that an attacker would gain this knowledge beforehand. We exploit that signals have several distinguishing statistical features which can be learnt and effectively used to identify them across different vehicles, that is, to quasi ”reverse-engineer” the CAN protocol. We also demonstrate that the extracted signals can be successfully used to re-identify individuals in a dataset of 33 drivers. Therefore, not revealing signal locations in CAN logs *per se* does not prevent them to be regarded as personal data of drivers.

We emphasize that we do not intend to perform (an even remotely) comprehensive reverse engineering [67]; we focus solely on a small number of sensor signals which are good descriptors of natural driving behavior.

Our contributions are three-fold:

1. we devise a heuristic method for message decomposition and log pre-processing;
2. we build, train and validate a machine learning classifier that can efficiently match vehicle sensor signals to a ground truth based on raw CAN data. In particular,

we train a classifier on the statistical features of a signal in one car (e.g., Opel Astra), then we use this trained classifier to localize the same signal in a different car (e.g., Toyota). The intuition is that the physical phenomenon represented by the signal has identical statistical features across different cars, and hence can be used to identify the same signal in all cars using the same classifier;

3. we briefly demonstrate that re-identification of drivers is possible using the extracted signals.

2.2.1 Related work

Driver characterization based on CAN data has gathered significant research interest from both the automotive and the data privacy domain. The common trait in these works is the presumed familiarity with the whole specific CAN protocol stack including the presentation and application layers giving the researchers access to sensor signals. This knowledge is usually gained via access to the OEM’s documentations in the framework of some research cooperation. As such, researchers do not normally disclose such information to preserve secrecy.

Miyajima et al. has investigated [56] driver characteristics when following another vehicle and pedal operation patterns were modeled using speech recognition methods. Sensor signals were collected in both a driving simulator and a real vehicle. Using car-following patterns and spectral features of pedal operation signals authors achieved an identification rate of 89.6% for the simulator (12 drivers). For the field test, by only applying cepstral analysis on pedal signals the identification rate was down to 76.8% (276 drivers). Fugiglando et al. [35] developed a new methodology for near-real-time classification of driver behavior in uncontrolled environments, where 64 people drove 10 cars for a total of over 2000 driving trips without any type of predetermined driving instruction. Despite their advance use of unsupervised machine learning techniques they conclude that clustering drivers based on their behavior remains a challenging problem.

Hallac et al. [43] discovered that driving maneuvers during turning exhibit personal traits that are promising regarding driver re-identification. Using the same dataset from Audi and its affiliates, Fugiglando et al. [36], showed that four behavioral traits, namely braking, turning, speeding and fuel efficiency could characterize driver adequately well. They provided a (mostly theoretical) methodology to reduce the vast CAN dataset along these lines.

Enev et al. authored a seminal paper [27] which makes use of mostly statistical features as an input for binary (one-vs-one) classification with regard to driving behavior. Driving the same car in a constrained parking lot setting and a longer but fixed route,

authors re-identified their 15 drivers with 100% accuracy. Authors had access to all available sensor signals and their scaling and offset parameters from the manufacturer’s documentation.

In a paper targeted at anomaly detection in in-vehicle networks [55], authors developed a greedy algorithm to split the messages into fields and to classify the fields into categories: constant, multi-value and counter/sensor. Note that the algorithm does not distinguish between counters and sensor signals, and the semantics of the signals are not interpreted. Thus, their results cannot be directly used for inferring driver behavior.

2.2.2 CAN data analysis

All recorded messages contained 4 to 8 bytes of data; this made it likely that multiple (potentially unrelated) pieces of information can be sent under the same ID. We first assumed that signals are positioned over whole bytes; this turned out to be wrong. Our investigation revealed that besides signal values a message can also contain constants, multi-value fields and counters. Some values appear only on-demand, such as windscreen or window signals. All data apart from sensor signals are considered noise and, therefore, need to be removed.

Meaningful CAN IDs vary significantly across vehicle makes and models, therefore we expected that the only signals found in all cars with high probability are the basic ones: such as velocity, brake, clutch and accelerator pedal positions, RPM (round per minute) and steering wheel angle. Next, we devise a method that yields a deeper understanding of the Data field in CAN messages and a possibility for sensor signal extraction. Note that from this point we will use the term ID as a reference to both a given type of message and its data stream (time series).

Bit decomposition heuristics

Extracting the signals from a CAN message is not a trivial challenge. While monitoring the data stream while driving and finding the exact bits that change in reaction to one’s actions is possible, it is highly time consuming, does not scale with hundreds of different existing CAN protocol versions and bound to miss out on potential sensor signals. (We only took this approach with a single car model to generate training data and a validation framework for our machine learning solution.) Our objective here is to present our observations on message types and distributions that leads to a smarter message decomposition method.

First, we examined the message streams literally bit-by-bit. We presumed that inside a given ID with potentially multiple sensor readings there was a difference in their bit

value distribution, hence they could be systematically located and partitioned according to some rule. E.g., let us assume that there are two signals sent next to each other under the same ID (i.e., there are no zero bits or other separators between the two. Given that signals are encoded in a big endian (little endian) format, both of their MSBs (LSBs) are rarely 1s. Therefore, there should be a drop in bit probability (i.e., the probability for a given bit to be 1) between the last bit of the first signal and the first bit of the second signal. In order to visualize these drops we represent IDs by their bit distribution: we sum the number of messages for each ID and how many times a given bit was one and divide these two measures:

$$v_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{|v|} \mathbb{1}_{\{v_j=1\}}}{|v|}$$

where v denotes the binary vector of a given ID, that is the representation of a CAN message's payload in binary format, and where v_i denotes the probability of a bit being 1 at the i^{th} position.

In 2.2a one of the bit distribution representation from one of our test car can be seen, here the messages are easily differentiable from each other. The figure to the right is slightly more complicated than the one to the left. It includes two constant parts and two counters (the platforms), we can easily exclude those as well.

Figure 2.2: Simple bit distribution

When we examined the distribution of the bits in an ID we found that in some cases it is straightforward to extract a signal: between two signal candidates there were separator bits with $v_i = 0$ or $v_i = 1$. Other cases were more complex: given Figure 2.3a it is hard to determine signal borders. However, combined with the bit distribution from the same ID and car model but another drive, the signals became clearly distinguishable.

Figure 2.3: Bit distribution of the same ID from different drivers

Pre-processing

After examining bit distributions we realized that $\approx 90\%$ of candidate signal blocks are placed on one or two bytes. In other cases signal borders were not unambiguous, see Figure 2.4. Our first heuristic suggests a start of a new signal because of the drop at the 23rd and the 24th bits, although it is clearly a counter or a constant on 3 bits, but we can not determine where exactly a new signal starts (is it the 28th bit or the 32nd?). Moreover, the 41th bit is constant 1 bit which might signify some kind of a separator, yet we cannot be certain. After a long evaluation we decided to divide the data part of the messages to bytes and pairs of bytes; as a result for one ID we could define 4 to 8 sensor candidates.

Filtering: Examining the byte time series resulting from the above approach, we spotted that many series were constant, had very few values, were cyclic (counters) or changed very rarely. As we intended to use machine learning to find the exact signals, not filtering these samples could have caused significant performance loss and a bloated and skewed training dataset with a lot of similar negative samples resulting in a decreased variability of training data potentially to a degree of corrupting the model. Therefore, we evaluated the variation for each sample and excluded those that had a very low variation ("low variation" was also a free variable optimized during evaluation).

Normalization: We scaled all candidate time series to the interval of $[0, 1]$: we extracted the maximum value for the whole candidate series, then we divided all values by the maximum. Scaling the data solves the problem of transformed (shifted) values, i.e., the same signal can take different values during drives, that can be a result of some transformation on the data in one vehicle or simply the fact that one car was driven in a lower range of

Figure 2.4: Consecutive blocks in a CAN message that cannot be unambiguously divided

velocity in contrast to the other (i.e., one log comes from a drive that did not exceed 50 km/h while the other rarely drove slower than 100 km/h).

Sliding windows: We divided logs into overlapping sliding windows from which we extracted our features for machine learning. The sliding window length (elapsed time) and percentage of overlap with previous and successive windows were free variables which we set to default values and subsequently optimized during run time.

2.2.3 Signal classification

We use machine learning for two purposes; first, to extract signals from CAN messages, and second, to perform driver re-identification using the extracted signals. Therefore, we build two different types of classifiers. In order to extract signals, we train a classifier per signal on the statistical features of the signal in a base car (e.g., Opel Astra 2018) where we exactly know where the signal resides, that is, the message ID and byte number of the CAN message which contains the signal. Then, we use the trained models to identify the same signals in another car (e.g., Toyota) where the locations of the signals (i.e., message ID and byte number) are unknown. The intuition is that the physical phenomenon that a signal represents has identical statistical features irrespective of the car, and hence can be used to identify the same signal in all cars using the same classifier.

For driver re-identification, similarly to previous works [35, 56], we use a separate classifier that is trained on the already extracted signals of the car. This classifier learns the

Table 2.3: Average feature importances

Feature	Importance
count below mean	0.2113
count above mean	0.1482
cid_ce	0.1290
mean abs change	0.1048
maximum	0.0716
longest strike below mean	0.0708

distinguishing features of different drivers (and not that of signals like the first classifier) using the signals produced during their drives.

For both signal extraction and driver re-identification, the features computed from each sliding window constitute a single training sample (i.e., a sample vector) used as the input of our machine learning classifiers. Below we describe the classifiers, the division of training and testing samples, and the method used for multi-class classification.

Multi-class Classification

We implemented multiclass classification using binary classification in a one-vs-rest way (aka, one-vs-all (OvA), one-against-all (OAA)). The strategy involves training a single classifier per class, with the samples of that class as positive samples and all other samples as negatives. For signal extraction, a class represents a pair of message ID and byte number, whereas for driver re-identification, it represents a driver’s identity. A random forest model was trained per class with balanced training data (i.e., containing the same number of positive and negative samples), and its output was binary indicating whether the input sample belongs to the class or not. For signal extraction, as each training/testing sample is a small portion of the time-series (i.e., window) representing a signal, we apply the trained model on all portions of a signal and obtain multiple decisions per signal. Then, the ”votes” are aggregated and the candidate signal with the most number of ”votes” is selected.

We would like to stress that random forests are indeed capable of general multiclass classification without its transformation to binary. We have also tried this general multiclassification approach, however, its results were inferior to the OvA’s results. Moreover successful driver re-identification can already be carried out using a single or only a few signals [27]. In this work, we use the velocity, the brake pedal, the accelerator pedal, the clutch pedal and the RPM signals to extract for driver re-identification.

Feature extraction

Our classifiers use statistical features of the samples; for each sliding window we extracted 20 different statistics that are widely considered as most descriptive regarding time series characteristics (see the best features in Table 2.3. We finally used 15 features based on their importances calculated from our random forest models. These features are the following:

1. *count_above_mean(x)*: Returns the number of values in x that are higher than the mean of x .
2. *count_below_mean(x)*: Returns the number of values in x that are lower than the mean of x .
3. *longest_strike_above_mean(x)*: Returns the length of the longest consecutive subsequence in x that is bigger than the mean of x .
4. *longest_strike_below_mean(x)*: Returns the length of the longest consecutive subsequence in x that is smaller than the mean of x .
5. *binned_entropy(x, max_bins)*: First bins the values of x into max_bins equidistant bins. The max_bin parameter was generally set to 10. Then calculates the value of:

$$-\sum_{k=0}^{\min(max_bins, len(x))} p_k \cdot \log(p_k) \cdot \mathbf{1}_{\{p_k > 0\}}$$

where p_k is the percentage of samples in bin k .

6. *mean_abs_change(x)*: Returns the mean over the absolute differences between subsequent time series values which is:

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1, \dots, n-1} |x_{i+1} - x_i|$$

7. *mean_change(x)*: Returns the mean over the differences between subsequent time series values which is:

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1, \dots, n-1} (x_{i+1} - x_i)$$

8. OTHER: minimum, maximum, mean, median, standard variation, variance, kurtosis, skewness

This way we created an input vector of features for each sample (one sample corresponds to one window). No smoothing, outlier elimination or function approximation are performed on the samples before feature extraction. For calculating the above statistics, we used the *tsfresh* python package².

Training and model optimization

For training our classifier we need to have a ground truth of sensor signals from a single car. These certified signals then can be compared to the candidate signals from other cars to find the best match. We chose the Opel Astra 2018 as our reference, as we had the most drives logged from this car.

Velocity versus GPS

We recorded GPS coordinates for all drives with the Opel Astra 2018. Setting the Android GPS Logger app to the highest accuracy (complemented by cell tower information achieving an accuracy of 3 meters) and saving the coordinates every second, we ended up with a time series of locations. Using the timestamps, GPS time series also determines the mean velocity between neighboring locations, producing a velocity time series. Intuitively, the GPS based velocity is very close to the one recorded from the CAN bus.

In order to test this hypothesis we applied the Dynamic Time Warp algorithm (DTW) [65]. The DTW algorithm is part of time series classification algorithms [5], their important characteristic being that there may be discriminatory features dependent on the ordering of the time series values [38]. A distance measurement between time series is needed to determine similarity between time series and for classification. Euclidean distance is an efficient distance measurement that can be used. The Euclidean distance between two time series is simply the sum of the squared distances from each n^{th} point in one time series to the n^{th} point in the other. The main disadvantage of using Euclidean distance for time series data is that its results are very un-intuitive. If two time series are identical, but one is shifted slightly along the time axis, then Euclidean distance may consider them to be very different from each other. DTW was introduced to overcome this limitation and give intuitive distance measurements between time series by ignoring both global and local shifts in the time dimension. DTW finds the optimal alignment between two time series if one time series may be warped non-linearly by stretching or shrinking it along its time axis.

Before running DTW we excluded the outliers from the GPS-based velocity series. These points are the result of GPS measurement error and materialize in extreme differ-

²<https://tsfresh.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Table 2.4: DTW velocity search top results

CAN ID	Byte	Distance
0410	1-2	7499
0410	2-3	15972
0295	1-2	20609
0510	2	20981
0510	3	21585

ences between two neighboring velocity values (we used 30 km/h as a limit). We then ran DTW with the GPS-based velocity values against all other sensor candidates of the CAN log. As the result of the DTW algorithm is a distance between two series, the smallest distance yields the best match: in every case it was indeed the same ID by a wide margin (see Table 2.4). We used manual physical tryouts to corroborate that this ID indeed corresponds to velocity.

Brake vs. accelerator: pedal position

Extracting the brake and the accelerator pedal positions required a different approach. In a normal vehicle the accelerator and the brake pedal are not pressed at the same time because it contradicts a driver’s normal behaviour (excluding race car drivers). Consequently, to extract the accelerator and the brake pedal positions one only have to search for a pair of signals that are almost exclusive to each other. For this end, we compared all pairs of ID byte subseries from multiple drives and listed the candidates that fit the description. Figure 2.5a shows the correct result and Figure 2.5b shows false candidate. False results were easy to exclude because of their characteristics; in this example it is trivial that a piece-wise constant signal cannot possibly signify a pedal position. Finally, we used manual physical tryouts to corroborate that these IDs indeed correspond to the brake and accelerator pedal positions, respectively. Note that older vehicles can have a binary brake (and clutch) signal, as there is no corresponding sensor signal in them.

Clutch vs. RPM vs. velocity

The clutch pedal position also has very typical characteristics especially when compared with the velocity and RPM values. Once we start to accelerate from 0km/h usually we change the gears quickly, thus the changes in the rpm and clutch pedal position are easy to detect. Upon gear change the RPM drops, then rises as we accelerate, then drops and rises again until we reach the desired gear and velocity. During the same time we push the clutch pedal every time just before the gear is changed. Moreover, we tend to use the clutch pedal in a very typical way, when the driver releases the clutch there is a slight slip around the middle position of the pedal indicating that the shafts start to connect.

(a) Brake pedal (black) vs. accelerator pedal (red) position

(b) A false match

Figure 2.5: Searching for the brake and accelerator pedal position signals

Figure 2.6: The clutch pedal position (black) vs. RPM (blue) vs. velocity (red) of one of our test vehicles.

(Note that the length of this slip is characteristic for car models, condition (e.g., bad clutch) and driver experience.) Applying this common knowledge we searched for a pair of signals with one of them having a sharp spike (RPM) and the other a small platform (slipping clutch) around the same time. We narrowed our search to cases when the vehicle accelerated from zero to at most 50 km/h. In Figure 2.6 we can see these signal characteristics compared to each other. We managed to find the clutch pedal position and RPM signals based on the above. As before, we validated our findings with manual physical tryouts.

Optimization

After extracting the ground truth signals, we calculated the feature vectors and trained a

random forest classifier for each extracted signal: velocity, brake pedal position, accelerator pedal position, clutch pedal position and engine RPM. For parameter optimization and testing we tested our model on logs from the same car, but driven by another driver on another route.

2.2.4 Results

Next we describe the performance of our classifiers used to extract signals from CAN logs and to re-identify drivers using the extracted signals.

Signal extraction

Our random forest classifiers used for signal extraction are trained on the CAN logs of a base car (here it is an Opel Astra'18) where the locations of a target signal is known. The classifiers take statistical data vectors as inputs with the 15 statistical features (see in Section 2.2.3) extracted from each sample (window). In particular, we train a random forest classifier to distinguish a target signal from all other signals, where the positive training samples are composed of the windows of the time series corresponding to the target signal, whereas negative samples are taken from other signals' time series. Hence, we obtain a classifier per target signal. Recall that signal locations are computed using the techniques described in Section 2.2.3. We apply each trained classifier on all the samples (windows) of all time series in another (target) car where we want to locate the corresponding target signals. For every classifier, we obtain a classification for each window of each time series in the target car. The time series which receives the largest number of votes (i.e., has the most windows classified as positive) will be the matched signal, i.e. the signal which is the most similar to the target signal.

Best results were obtained using the following parameter settings: the length of windows is set to 2.5 seconds, which is sufficiently large to capture different driver reactions (one can accelerate from 0 to even 30 km/h or can hit the brakes and stop the vehicle). The sampled logs are at least 30 minutes long, the overlap parameter is set to 25%. The pruning parameter is set to 7, i.e. a sample was excluded when its variation is less than 7. The rationale behind this value is the following: we have enumerated all the different values occurring in one candidate sample and observed that the counters usually have at most 10-15 values, but having a short sample could mean that one counter can not make a full cycle during that interval. Counters also have different frequencies thus we could not use a general rule that fits all messages, but using the value of 7 worked well in practice.

Each trained random forest classifier is tested against samples from logs of all other

cars except the base car, and the logs were pre-processed as described in Section 2.2.2. The matching performed by a classifier is validated by manually extracting the ground truth sensor signal from the target car as described in Section 2.2.3. In order to measure the accuracy of our classifier, we report the rank of the true signal; each candidate signal is ranked according to the number of votes (i.e., positive classifications) they receive, i.e. the signal having the highest vote ranked first.

Table 2.5 shows the results of signal extraction using only 30 minutes of data for training and also 30 minutes for matching (testing), where training was performed on CAN logs obtained from our base car (i.e., Opel Astra’18). Three signals (RPM, velocity and accelerator pedal position) are all ranked in the first place (i.e. received the highest number of votes in the classifier), that is, *our approach successfully identified all three signals in all the target cars*. Note that we did not extract the clutch and the brake pedal position signals as during the validation we realized that these signals do not even exist in most of our cars in the database.

We also report the precision ($TP/TP+FP$) and recall ($TP/TP+FN$) of the classifier (where TP =true positive, FP =false positive and FN =false negative) which represent how many positive classifications are correct over all samples of all time-series in the CAN log (precision), and how many samples of the true matching signal are correctly recognized by the classifier (recall). We also compute and report the gap which is the difference between the number of votes (i.e., positive classifications) of the highest ranked true signal and that of the highest ranked false signal divided by the total number of votes. For example if the highest ranked true signal received 50% of the votes and the highest ranked false signal received 20%, then the gap equals 0.30. Note that in most cars most sensors appear under several IDs in the log, this causes that more than one candidate with very high votes are all true positives, thus the top high ranks can all be true positives and the highest ranked false signal drops to the fourth, fifth or even lower places.

Also note that the false positive rate is relatively high, those votes scatter across different candidates (IDs), whereas the true positive(s) always get the most votes. In most cars some sensors appear under several IDs in a log, this causes that more than one candidate with very high votes are all true positives. Table 2.5 only depicts the highest vote, and in the last column the first real gap, that is the gap between the votes of the first false positive and the true positive above that. (For example the first 3 IDs with the highest votes are all true positives, and the 4th is the first false positive in line, the *gap* signifies the difference in the votes of the 3rd and 4th highest.)

Table 2.5: Top results against RPM, velocity and acceleration

Sensor	Rank	Precision	Recall	Gap
Citroen_rpm	1	0.353	0.952	0.180
Citroen_velo	1	0.874	0.792	0.094
Citroen_acc	1	0.740	0.444	0.431
Opel_A06_rpm	1	0.155	0.604	0.035
Opel_A06_velo	1	0.158	0.969	0.024
Opel_A06_acc	1	0.207	0.934	0.026
Toyota_A_rpm	1	0.229	0.717	0.238
Toyota_A_velo	1	0.230	0.214	0.337
Toyota_A_acc	1	0.394	0.566	0.296
Toyota_C_rpm	1	0.224	0.399	0.049
Toyota_C_velo	1	0.676	0.139	0.029
Toyota_C_acc	1	0.602	0.522	0.134
Renault_rpm	1	0.439	0.991	0.148
Renault_velo	1	0.890	0.522	0.465
Renault_acc	1	0.491	0.702	0.210
Nissan_X_rpm	1	0.248	0.805	0.140
Nissan_X_velo	1	0.970	0.870	0.466
Nissan_X_acc	1	0.484	0.728	0.527
Nissan_Q_rpm	1	0.211	0.680	0.034
Nissan_Q_velo	1	0.462	0.522	0.110
Nissan_Q_acc	1	0.512	0.774	0.044

Driver re-identification

Next we use the extracted signals in a driver re-identification scenario. We use the same preprocessing as in Section 2.2.2 and the same parameter settings as in Section 2.2.3, except that we do not use all 15 features, only 11 of them are chosen based on their importances: *count above mean*, *count below mean*, *longest strike above mean*, *longest strike below mean*, *maximum*, *mean*, *mean abs change*, *median*, *minimum*, *standard deviation*, *variance*. We used four extracted signals: accelerator and brake pedal positions, velocity and RPM. The feature vector of a driver consists of 44 features altogether. All drivers used the same car, which was Opel Astra'18, to produce CAN logs. The samples were divided into a training and testing set, where the training and testing data made 90% and 10% of all samples, respectively. We used 10-fold cross-validation to evaluate our approach. We selected 5 drivers uniformly at random, and built a binary classifier for each pair of drivers. Our classifier achieved 77% precision on average (each model was evaluated 10 times). The worst result was just under 70% and the best result was 87%.

2.2.5 Summary

We described a technique to extract signals from vehicles' CAN logs. Our approach relies on using unique statistical features of signals which remain mostly unchanged even between different types of cars, and hence can be used to locate the signals in the CAN log. Our results show that having a database of CAN signals (for example extracted from the attacker's own car) one can extract these signals from a given CAN log file. We demonstrated that the extracted signals can be used to effectively identify drivers in a dataset of 33 drivers. Although our results need to be evaluated on a larger and more diverse dataset, our findings show that driver re-identification can be performed without the nuisance of signal extraction or agreements with a manufacturer. This means that not revealing the exact signal location in CAN logs is not sufficient to provide any privacy guarantee in practice. Car companies should devise more principled (perhaps cryptographic) approaches to hide signals, and/or to anonymize their CAN logs so that drivers cannot be re-identified. The assessment of the extracted signals in the driver re-identification scenario also show positive results, but this problem needs to be researched with different and more fitting methods.

2.3 Automatic Driver Identification from In-Vehicle Network Logs

As we have seen it in the previous section, reverse engineering signals needs ground truth data that can be tedious to gather, and even after we collected the data the extraction of the descriptive signals can be tiresome and time consuming. Not to mention that CAN data collection is often considered to be illegal [12]. A straightforward question could be if it was possible to re-identify drivers without the need of reverse engineering signals? This scenario calls for a weaker attacker, in the followings, we assume that the adversary has access to raw CAN data, but does not aim for reverse engineering the protocol, this can be due to the lack of necessary skills or simply time.

In addition, we have to consider that upcoming autonomous cars produce and may share an order of magnitude larger amount of real-time data (≈ 1 GB/s) than traditional cars. Indeed, data from vehicles are predicted to create a \$10 trillion market and could become five times bigger than the market for the cars themselves in the next few years³. With this in mind, any solution must be scalable to such large datasets.

³bit.ly/2V14YkK

In this section, we show that there is no need to reverse-engineer the CAN protocol to identify drivers. In addition, re-identification remains feasible without significantly constraining the driving environment (as it was done in previous works [28, 44, 56, 78]); what’s more, such inference is practical with off-the-shelf machine learning techniques readily available to anybody. This is a plausible scenario when a malicious actor gains access to the car’s CAN bus through an Internet-connected device such as a smartphone using a wired or wireless data collector adapter plugged into the car’s OBD-II connector [68].

For the purpose of inference, we blindly consider all possible time series that could be easily extracted from CAN logs without any sort of manual inspection of their content. We use machine learning techniques to select time series with sufficient predictive power and use their combination for classification. Our solution is scalable and does not require reverse-engineering the proprietary communication protocol used on the CAN bus.

Our specific contributions are twofold:

- We demonstrate the feasibility of driver re-identification even if drivers follow different routes and the exact signals (such as velocity, acceleration, RPM, etc.) cannot be extracted directly from the captured CAN log. We extract a time series from every byte of every CAN message, from which the ones with the most predictive power are identified. In particular, we build a convolution-based neural network, where features from individual time series are learnt automatically by convolutional layers, which are then combined in a mixture model in order to perform the final classification. We achieve a mean accuracy of driver classification between 75-85% for CAN traces with a length of less than 2 minutes. By contrast, most prior works [44, 28] achieved comparable result only with fewer drivers (2-15) and when the exact signals could be extracted and are readily available for classification.
- We propose a scalable technique to classify a large set of time series even if many of the individual time series are significantly noisy and hence lack sufficient predictive power individually. Our approach first classifies each time series separately, and combines the best performing individual models to classify the whole set of time series.

2.3.1 Neural Networks for Automatic Feature Extraction

Convolutional Neural Networks

In recent years, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have significantly progressed the fields of audio and visual pattern recognition [53]. CNNs are capable of automatically

learning complex feature representations using their convolutional layers. Specifically, CNNs produce a set of (learnable) filters that can recognize patterns in a translation-invariant way. Suppose f is a filter (or vector) with size n and T is a time series also represented by a vector of values. Then, the 1-dimensional discrete convolution of f and T is given by

$$(T * f)[i] = \sum_{j=1}^n f[n+1-j] \cdot T[i+j-1]$$

Filters are learnt in order to extract different features from the time series using convolution. For instance, if $f = [1, -1]$, $T * f$ equals the gradient (i.e., difference) between any two neighboring points. Hence, there is no need to manually craft such features since the value of $T * f$ (or its simple functions such as maximum or average) is used as "features" and are further fed into a classification model. By changing the number and size of filters as well as stacking multiple convolution layers, a CNN can learn to detect many different local traits of a time series. For example, if T is the velocity, then convolving T with $f = [1, -1]$ yields the acceleration. Therefore, by applying max pooling on the convolved signal the model can learn to distinguish drivers based on their maximum acceleration. Although, in theory, CNN could learn many different transformations of the time series such as discrete Fourier transform, such specific functions are almost never learnt in practice [58]. It is still an open question what exact functions are learnable by CNNs.

If $(T * f)$ is evaluated at every point of T , then the same feature represented by f can be detected along the whole time series T . This makes CNNs particularly suitable to detect local features. Indeed, most drivers exhibit only local distinguishing features (e.g., the short moments when they accelerate or decelerate) as the signal is globally shaped by traffic conditions rather than by the driver's behaviour.

CNNs are also more scalable than traditional fully connected neural networks (FCNNs), because the same filters are applied along the whole time series, that is, the number of learnable parameters is proportional to the number and size of filters and not to the size $|T|$ of the whole time series. This also makes CNNs less prone to overfitting.

Long Short Term Memory Networks

A Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) uses memory to model short-term dependencies in sequential data. When folded out in time, it can be considered as a feedforward deep neural network with indefinitely many layers. New information is added in every iteration step, and the network can pass this information on for an infinite number of network

updates, by this the RNN essentially yield unlimited memory depth. RNNs generally receive input and produce output at each time step. In itself, the network updates do not guarantee hierarchical processing of the information, only in regard that earlier data (provided various time steps ago) passes through the network more often. Long-term temporal dependencies are difficult to model with RNNs because the gradient of the loss function decays exponentially with time (the vanishing gradient problem). i.e., with each subsequent layer the magnitude of the gradients gets exponentially smaller (vanishes) thus making the steps also very small which results in very slow learning of the weights in the lower layers of a deep network. Another weakness of common RNNs is that they do not explicitly support multiple time scales, and any temporal hierarchy that is present in the input signal needs to be embedded implicitly in the network. However, time series often have a temporal hierarchy, where the information is scattered over multiple time scales. Common RNNs, however, do not explicitly allow for such a hierarchy, this shapes the core motivation for Long Short-Term memory (LSTM) networks [49], a special type of RNNs, overcome the above problems. The recurrent weights in an LSTM (learnt during the training phase) select which information they need to pass onwards vs. which they need to discard. A common LSTM unit is composed of a cell, an input gate, an output gate and a forget gate. The cell remembers values over arbitrary time intervals, while the three gates regulate the flow of information into and out of the cell.

2.3.2 Inference model

We extract a time series from every byte of every CAN message, from which the ones with the most predictive power are identified. In particular, we build a convolution-based neural network, where features from individual time series are learnt automatically by convolutional layers, which are then combined in a mixture model in order to perform the final classification.

It is premised is that the signals represented by the time series are unknown, therefore, for the purpose of inference, we use an artificial neural network (ANN), where the features of a time series are automatically extracted and learnt by multiple convolution layers. This is advantageous as the manual feature extraction of an unknown signal would be difficult otherwise.

We propose a mixture model with two main components:

1. **Individual time series (ITS) model:** This model is specialized to the classification of a single time series. We build one ITS model per time series, hence we obtain N different ITS models altogether, where N is the number of all time series. A time series is extracted by concatenating the same byte of every CAN message

with identical message ID.

2. **Mixture model:** The already trained ITS models are combined into a single fully connected decision/output layer which provides the final classification result.

Importantly, ITS models are trained individually and separately from the mixture model, which makes our solution scalable. In particular, each ITS model can be trained independently and in parallel, and the training of the whole mixture model does not require to fine-tune or re-train the already trained ITS models. Once ITS models are trained, their weights are frozen and not modified during the training of their mixture model.

Next, we describe the model architecture in more details. The architecture of our proposal is illustrated in Figure 2.8 and in Figure 2.7

2.3.3 Data augmentation

We first divide the time series into equally-sized segments, from here on referred to as samples. Given a single sample as input, our model attempts to classify it into its correct class (e.g., driver ID). Due to the limited amount of data, and similarly to prior works [18, 76], we use a sliding window over the whole time series to create samples. Specifically, let $T = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{|T|})$ denote a time series, and let $T_{i:j} = (t_i, t_{i+1}, \dots, t_j)$ be a window of T between positions i and j ($1 \leq i \leq j \leq |T|$). Then, the set of all n samples created from T is given by $\{T_{1:n}, T_{1+\ell, n+\ell}, \dots, T_{|T|-\ell+1, |T|}\}$, that is, all consecutive windows shifted by ℓ time slots.

This set is further divided into a training and a testing set so that their samples do not overlap. For example, if the size of the testing set is $|T| - \ell$, then $\{T_{1:n}, T_{1+s:n+s}, \dots, T_{1+(\ell-1)s-\lceil n/s \rceil: 1+(\ell-1)s-\lceil n/s \rceil+n}\}$ and $\{T_{\ell, \ell+n}, T_{1+s, n+s}, \dots, T_{k-s+1-\lceil n/s \rceil, n-\lceil n/s \rceil}\}$ comprise the training and testing set

2.3.4 Individual Time Series (ITS) Model

We use a CNN combined with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [49]. Our ITS model is inspired by [76]; however, it also differs in several aspects as we explain in Section 2.3.9.

First, the input sample is divided into equally-sized *non-overlapping* k segments. Each segment s_i of a sample is transformed into a higher-level representation/features $\text{CNN}(s_i)$ using the same CNN model. The CNN model is composed of two 1-dimensional convolutional layers (with Rectified Linear Unit activations), which are separated by a max pooling layer in order to reduce model complexity, and a fully connected layer producing the output of the CNN. The segment size should be sufficiently large in order

to capture any human driving reaction (e.g., acceleration, deceleration, gear switching, etc.), but still small enough to focus on distinctive driver features.

As the ITS model is applied on each segment of the sample independently, it can only model local features of a segment except for the sequential information along the sequence of segments as well as any global features of the whole sample. For this reason, we use an LSTM layer (with `tanh` activation) and it is applied on the sequence of local features extracted by CNN. In particular, a single CNN model is used to extract features from every segment s_i . The sequence of these representations are further processed by LSTM, which computes time-dependent features by transforming the input sequence into another sequence h_1, h_2, \dots, h_k composed of the hidden states of the LSTM model. Specifically, for input segment s_i , $h_i = \text{LSTM}(\text{CNN}(s_i), h_{i-1})$. A hidden state h_i is produced for every input segment s_i , dependent on the current input as well as all previous input segments through h_{i-1} . The sequence of h_1, h_2, \dots, h_k is fed into an attention layer in order to select those parts of the sequence which represent distinctive driver features. In particular, a sample may contain only a few segments with clear distinctive features of the drivers such as a unique pattern of speeding, steering, or braking, while the rest may lack any unique driving pattern and hence bearing less importance in distinguishing drivers.

LSTM is ineffective to model sequential dependencies if the input sequence is too long (i.e., there are too many segments), which is alleviated by attention as follows. Several attention mechanisms have been proposed in the literature mainly for text classification and machine translation [7, 63]. In this work, we use a simple mechanism [63] which provides the best performance for our dataset. The attention mechanism computes the weighted average of all the hidden states h_1, h_2, \dots, h_k produced by LSTM along the whole input sequence. More specifically, the attention mechanism is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &= \tanh(w^\top h_i + b) \\ \alpha_i &= \frac{\exp(u_i)}{\sum_i \exp(u_i)} \\ a &= \sum_i \alpha_i h_i \end{aligned}$$

where $w \in \mathbb{R}^k$ and $b \in \mathbb{R}$ are jointly learnt parameters, and a_i is the attention vector which represents sample i . In essence, a is the weighted average of each segment’s LSTM representation, where the weights are a non-linear function of these representations. This function is modeled by a shallow neural network with weights w and bias b . w is initialized with random values drawn from a Gaussian distribution with a mean of zero and standard deviation $\sqrt{1/k}$, whereas bias b is initialized to 0.

Finally, the attention vector a is provided to a fully connected layer with `tanh` activa-

tion, whose output is then given to a final softmax (multi-class classification) or a sigmoid layer (binary classification). If v represent the output of the model, then the decision is given by $\arg \max_i v_i$. We apply dropout regularization on every fully connected layer of our model. If the classification problem is binary, we use a sigmoid layer and optimize against a binary cross-entropy error function. When the classification problem is multi-class, we use softmax as the final layer with categorical cross-entropy as a measure of classification error.

Attention layer

Many windows of sample are likely to be governed by patterns that are primarily influenced by road or traffic conditions and less by the driver itself. For example, driving in rural areas has very different global statistics (e.g., average speed or acceleration, fuel consumption) than driving in urban areas. Our focus is to identify drivers independently of the followed route.

In other words, our purpose to identify those patterns of a trace that is a clear distinctive feature of the drivers and not that of the trips.

2.3.5 Mixture model

ITS models classify individual time series and therefore each can have very different predictive performance. Indeed, some time series contain more distinctive driver features (e.g., brake pedal position) than others (e.g., velocity). In fact, it turns out that the majority of time series often do not have any predictive power at all.

We combine ITS models into a single Mixture model by connecting all ITS models to the same fully-connected neural layer, called mixture layer, whose output provides the final prediction. We first remove the output layer of the already trained ITS models, and merge the remaining part into the mixture layer. Finally, the whole mixture model is trained by adjusting the weights of only the mixture layer while keeping all parameters of the individual models intact. In case there are too many ITS models and the training of the mixture model is not feasible due to memory constraints, only the top-K best performing ITS models are used in the mixture. Also, the trained ITS models can be compressed by distillation [48].

In fact, our mixture model is a sort of committee machine [45], where multiple neural networks, called as experts, are combined to provide the final classification. Indeed, each ITS model is an expert which is specialized to extract a high-level representation of a single time-series. These representations are non-linearly combined to produce the classification.

(a) Layers of the sample model applied on a single sample

(b) Layers of the window model applied on a every consecutive window.

Figure 2.7: Our neural network used to infer driver’s identity and personal attributes.

The benefit of the mixture layer is to model inter-dependencies between different time series which may improve classification accuracy. For example, the acceleration and deceleration patterns individually may not be unique to a driver but their combination is.

Note that our mixture model is not a simple ensemble of the ITS models, as we remove their output layer before adding them to the mixture and we do not train the whole mixture together but only the mixture layer.

Figure 2.8: Our mixture model.

2.3.6 Evaluation

In this section, we evaluate our mixture model described in Section 2.3.2. The applied dataset have been described in Section 2.1.1

2.3.7 Extracting time series from CAN logs

The CAN logs of all drivers contain 53 different message IDs from which we extract 72 different time series per driver. More specifically, we consider all single bytes of every message, and a single time series corresponds to the series of bytes retrieved from the same byte position of all consecutive messages with the same message ID, which is also illustrated in Table 2.1. We dropped all time series (1) with a single constant value in all time slots, (2) that were too short, (3) contained the values of counters. We retained the time series which occur in each driver’s trace. This pre-processing finally yields 72 time series per driver. Accordingly, we built 72 different ITS models, each corresponding to a single time series. The validation accuracy of each ITS model is evaluated, and the top-10 best performing ITS models are selected and used in the mixture model.

Training and Testing data

In order to train an ITS model which is specialized for the classification of a single time series, we build two datasets \mathbb{T} and \mathbb{S} , which are further used to create the training and testing datasets for any classification problem as follows.

First, each time series of every driver is divided into two parts. Samples extracted from the first part of every trace, using the sliding window technique described in Section 2.3.3, are added to \mathbb{T} . \mathbb{S} is created analogously from the second part of every trace. Since the size of the first part is always set to 80% of the whole trace, the training samples will roughly cover 80% of all the samples from all drivers. Training data is obtained by picking an identical number of samples per class from \mathbb{T} , and testing data is generated from \mathbb{S} . These guarantee that (1) the training and testing sets do not overlap, (2) training data is always balanced, and (3) the proportion of samples from a driver is identical both in the training and the testing data (i.e., there is no dataset shift).

Hyperparameters

Sample sizes are varied among 20, 60, and 120 seconds, and consecutive samples are shifted by 0.1s. For ITS models, samples are divided into non-overlapping segments with a size of 3 seconds, which is believed to be sufficient to capture the most important driving actions. Each convolutional layer has a kernel size corresponding to 0.5 seconds with a

stride of 0.05 seconds. The first convolution layer has 20 filters while the second layer applied on the output of the first layer has 40 filters followed by batch normalization [50]. Max pooling is applied on the result of every 5 consecutive convolution operations of the first layer. All FCNNs are composed of 64 units, and the number of LSTM’s hidden states is 16. ITS models are trained as long as validation accuracy improved: 2 epochs for ITS models and 4 epochs for the Mixture model on average. All models are trained with RMSprop⁴ with a fixed learning rate of 0.001. The output layers use softmax activation for multi-class classification and sigmoid activation for binary classification, which are optimized against categorical and binary cross-entropy, respectively, for all models.

2.3.8 Results

We use the model described in Section 2.3.2 for all classification tasks⁵. To measure performance on the testing data, we define testing accuracy as all correct classifications (TP+TN, True Positive plus True Negative) divided by all classifications:

$$\text{Acc} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{All}}$$

One-vs-all

Table 2.6 shows the re-identification accuracy in the 1-vs-all scenario, i.e., when one driver is distinguished from all other drivers with a single binary mixture model. We show the mean value over all 33 drivers (i.e., the mean accuracy over all the 33 models), standard deviation, and the extreme values for a specific driver. It is easy to see that accuracy improves sublinearly with the length of the sample trace, the mean ranging from 75% up to 85%. Maximum accuracy values for the most correctly classified driver are between 95% and 100%, while minimum values for the hardest-to-classify driver are between 43% and 46%.

Table 2.7 depicts the 1-vs-all re-identification accuracy depending on the personal attribute values, which include gender, age, and driving experience. Interestingly, the most experienced drivers are the easiest to distinguish from all the other drivers with a mean accuracy of 86%, which shows that, by practicing, people tend to develop more unique skill sets. This phenomenon has also been confirmed in other domains [51]. Similarly, female drivers seem to have more unique driving style than males, though the number of

⁴www.cs.toronto.edu/~tijmen/csc321/slides/lecture_slides lec6.pdf

⁵We implemented our model in Python 3.6.7 using the framework of Keras 2.2.2. Evaluation was done on commodity hardware with Intel Core i7-4770 CPU and 32 GB RAM, where the average time training of a mixture model is 294 sec, and one ITS is trained in 157 sec on average. A powerful GPU can considerably speed up training.

Table 2.6: Re-identification accuracy: 1-vs-all

<i>Sample length</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std.dev.</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>Min</i>
20 s	0.758	0.017	0.949	0.432
60 s	0.829	0.019	0.995	0.436
120 s	0.847	0.025	1.000	0.465

Table 2.7: Re-id. accuracy: 1-vs-all, sample length: 60 secs

<i>Attribute</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>Persons</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>Min</i>
Gender	Male	28	0.814	0.140	0.995	0.436
	Female	5	0.911	0.099	0.968	0.734
Age	[20-25]	11	0.840	0.106	0.939	0.573
	[25-30]	8	0.788	0.184	0.973	0.436
	[30-40]	7	0.892	0.143	0.995	0.606
	[40-70]	7	0.806	0.126	0.969	0.586
Experience	Low	12	0.834	0.108	0.968	0.573
	Average	11	0.799	0.172	0.964	0.436
	High	10	0.860	0.135	0.995	0.586

female drivers is too small in order to be conclusive.

Many-vs-all

Fig. 2.9 shows the re-identification accuracy in the many-vs-all scenario, i.e., when a group of drivers is distinguished from all other drivers with a single multi-class mixture model, further characterizing the performance of our method. In the 2-vs-all case, we randomly select 50 different groups of 2 drivers out of the possible $\binom{33}{2}$, and plot the mean value and the standard deviation; we do similarly with group sizes of 4, 10 and 33 (with only 1 possible allocation in the last, all-vs-all case). Notice that all-vs-all corresponds to the case when each driver is distinguished from each other using a single model. We observe that the mean value of accuracy is higher when the group size is smaller, ranging from the highest mean of 40% (all-vs-all, trace length 60 s) up to 91% (2-vs-all, trace length 20 s). It is interesting that a larger sample length does not always translate into higher accuracy; in fact, in almost all displayed cases the highest mean accuracy comes from models built on 60 s long samples (the exception to the rule is the 4-vs-all case, where the 120 s sample length yields slightly better results). Note that even in the hardest, all-vs-all case, our approach provides a 13-fold accuracy improvement compared to the $1/33 = 3.03\%$ baseline.

Figure 2.9: Re-identification accuracy: many-vs-all

2.3.9 Related work

In this section, we give an overview on the related work with regard to driver re-identification and neural network based time series classification.

Driver re-identification

Driver characterization based on driving data has gathered significant research interest from both the automotive control and the data privacy domain. In automotive control, substantial research efforts were made in modeling and recognizing driver behavior based on CAN and other driving data with the objective of designing and improving intelligent vehicle systems and providing enhanced driver safety features [72, 54]. On the other hand, the potential re-identification of drivers (i.e., singling out) based on recorded CAN data also became a focus for data privacy research [28]. The common trait in these works is the presumed familiarity with the specific CAN protocol stack including the presentation and application layers giving the researchers access to sensor signals. This knowledge is usually gained via access to the OEM’s documentations in the framework of some research cooperation. As such, researchers do not disclose such information to honor their contract and preserve confidentiality.

Miyajima et al. [56] collected and investigated sensor signals in both a driving simulator and a real vehicle. Using car-following patterns and spectral features of pedal operation signals authors achieved an identification rate of 89.6% for the simulator (12 drivers) and 76.8% (276 drivers) for the field test.

Hallac et al. [43] discovered that maneuvers during turning could fingerprint drivers using a dataset provided by Audi. Via the same dataset, Fugiglando et al. [36] showed that four behavioral traits, namely braking, turning, speeding and fuel efficiency could

characterize a driver adequately well.

Zhang et al. [78] developed a driver classification model based on both CAN and mobile phone sensor data. While effective for distinguishing between pairs of drivers, authors claim that their method does not scale well.

Enev et al. [28] make use of mostly statistical features as an input for binary (one-vs-one) classification with regard to driving behavior. These binary classifiers are combined into a multi-class classifier, which is not a scalable approach if there is a large number of drivers. Driving the same car in a constrained parking lot setting and a longer but fixed route, authors re-identified their 15 drivers with 100% accuracy. Authors had access to all available sensor signals and their scaling and offset parameters from the manufacturer’s documentation.

Fugiglando et al. [35] developed a new methodology for near-real-time classification of driver behavior in an uncontrolled setting. Despite their advanced use of unsupervised machine learning techniques they conclude that clustering drivers based on their behavior remains a challenging problem.

Remarks: Notice that if drivers follow different routes, then re-identification can be harder but also easier depending on the driving conditions compared to the case when drivers drive on the same route. This is because the extracted features may be that of the driving condition (i.e., traffic and road conditions), or the driver itself. For instance, if all drivers follow the same route then driver features are much easier to identify if the driving conditions are mostly unchanged among different drivers. This was also confirmed in [44], where the authors observed that drivers are easier to identify in rural areas than urban ones due to the more consistent driving conditions. On the other hand, if only a single driver drives in traffic jams, than its re-identification is much easier than that of the others due to the frequent slow-downs and accelerations. Still, in practice, it is much more likely that different drivers drive on different routes, hence we use this assumption in this work.

Time series classification with neural networks

The field of time series classification (TSC) has proposed a multitude of algorithms. These algorithms are either distance-based, using k-NN classifiers over distance measures between time series; or feature-based, extracting deterministic features in either the time domain or spectrum and applying traditional classification algorithms. Lately, ensemble methods using multiple classifiers have also been studied. An overview and comparative performance evaluation of these methods are presented in [6]. Using neural networks is a novel direction in TSC [18, 73, 46, 32]. In order to perform adequately, these methods require either additional pre-processing of the input signals or very large datasets. For a

comparative performance evaluation we refer the reader to the work of Fawaz et al. [32].

Our proposed classifier is most similar to the DeepSense framework [76] and the Multi-channels Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (MC-DCNN) [81]. Both works use CNNs to extract features from multiple time series which are fed into a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) [81] or a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) [76]. Our mixture model can be considered as a synergy of these two approaches. Unlike DeepSense [76] which applies 2 dimensional convolution on multiple time series, we apply 1 dimensional convolution on individual time series which are then combined in a fully connected layer as in MC-DCNN. We found this approach to be superior especially if many of the input time series are noisy and have no predictive power at all. Our approach can also be used to localize the parts of CAN messages which indeed identify a driver. Our model is also simpler (has fewer parameters) and hence is less prone to overfitting. Unlike MC-DCNN, we use LSTM with an attention layer per time series to focus on its most distinctive parts.

2.3.10 Summary

Our study demonstrates that driver re-identification remains feasible even without the manual inspection of messages captured on the CAN bus. In other words, profiling drivers can be performed even without reverse-engineering the CAN protocol.

The empirical evaluation of our approach on a dataset of 33 drivers demonstrates that a driver can be recognized with a success probability of 85% based on a mere 2 minutes of driving in urban areas, even if drivers follow different routes. Our findings include that drivers with substantial experience are the easiest to distinguish. As features are extracted automatically using convolutional neural networks, we conjecture that our technique is also applicable to predicting various other driver attributes such as age, gender, or driving experience; however, the necessary empirical justification would require a significantly larger dataset.

Chapter 3

Location Data Privacy

Analyzing human mobility patterns has been in the focus of both researchers and practitioners in the last decades [39] [10] [20]. Having created an already \$12 billion market, the location data industry is steadily expanding with companies that harvest, sell, or trade in location data. Many of these firms claim that privacy has utmost importance in their businesses and that they never sell personal data.¹

However, collecting and mining location data come inherently with their own strong privacy and other ethical concerns [9]. Several studies have shown that pseudonymization and quasi-standard de-identification are not sufficient to prevent users from being re-identified in location datasets [19] [77]. This significantly hinders location data sharing and use by researchers, developers and humanitarian workers alike².

Although a plethora of different anonymization techniques have been proposed for location data (for a very thorough survey see [33]), they all suffer from either weak utility, or weak privacy guarantees, or they are not scalable to large datasets. Indeed, location data are inherently high-dimensional and often sparse, which makes an individual's location trace unique even in very large populations³. This has a detrimental effect on privacy, and also on utility due to the curse of dimensionality. Note that aggregation per se does not necessarily prevent such re-identification in practice [75, 62]. The brittleness of privacy guarantees ignited research towards location anonymization with provable privacy guarantees. So far, only a handful of prior works [17, 47, 42, 11] have addressed the off-line anonymization of complete location trajectories with formal privacy guarantees. Most of these approaches use some form of Differential Privacy [25], which has become the *de facto* privacy model recent years [29, 2, 69].

¹<https://themarkup.org/privacy/2021/09/30/theres-a-multibillion-dollar-market-for-your-phones-location-data>

²<https://www.economist.com/leaders/2014/10/23/call-for-help>

³Four data points—approximate places and times where an individual was present—have been demonstrated to be enough to uniquely re-identify 95% of the users in a dataset of 1.5 million users [19]

Unfortunately, off-line location anonymization with Differential Privacy often implies serious accuracy degradation which can make anonymized data useless in practice. In particular, most schemes follow the common three-steps approach to generate privacy preserving synthetic location traces: (1) finding a faithful generative model of the underlying data generating distribution, (2) adding noise to the training of this model in order to provide Differential Privacy, (3) generating synthetic location trajectories from the noisy generative model. Generally, inaccuracy stems from either using a sub-optimal generative model, or a model which is not sufficiently robust against the additional noise needed for Differential Privacy. Although a more complex model is capable of faithfully capturing the peculiarities of location data, it also requires larger perturbation for privacy owing to the increased number of its parameters. Moreover, complex models very often are not scalable to larger datasets with several hundreds of thousands of location trajectories [11, 47]. Finally, to the best of our knowledge, none of these differentially private anonymization approaches release the valuable fine-grained temporal characteristics of location visits.

In this chapter, we propose a novel off-line anonymization scheme called DP-Loc for location data with strong Differential Privacy guarantees. Unlike prior works, we tackle high dimensional data modeling with generative neural networks (GNN) which have shown great promise recently. GNNs have the potential to automatically learn the general features of a location dataset including complex regularities such as the subtle and valuable correlation among different location visits as a function of time. The key of our approach is a novel decomposition of the generator model into a sequence of smaller models and a post-processing step, which are robust against perturbation needed for Differential Privacy, and therefore can be used to generate high-fidelity synthetic location trajectories. In particular, we first project all trajectories to a smaller set of frequent locations thereby reducing the dimensionality of the data. Then, a synthetic trace is created by first generating its source and destination along with time information, and then finding a path on a transition graph between these endpoints. Both the endpoint and graph generation are modelled by distinct neural networks scalable for being trained with differentially private gradient descent [1].

DP-Loc has several advantages. First, projecting traces to a smaller set of locations helps generalization and also increases robustness against the added noise. Second, separating endpoint from path generation preserves the length of trajectories more accurately compared to related work. Third, recently proposed advanced composition theorems of Differential Privacy [1] enable us to use differentially private neural networks with better utility instead of simple Markovian models [42, 17], and quantify the privacy guarantee of DP-Loc more accurately. Finally, neural networks are sufficiently flexible to model transi-

tion probabilities depending on the destination and time, which facilitates the generation of more realistic location traces. Figure 3.5 illustrates the power of DP-Loc, where the density of complete synthetic location trajectories produced by DP-Loc are compared to the original data and a state-of-the-art solution from [42].

Our specific contributions are as follows:

1. We propose a novel generative model, DP-Loc to generate realistic location trajectories with time information. A Variational Auto-Encoder (VAE) is used to generate the source and destination of a trace along with a single timestamp of the trace. Then, a feed-forward neural network is built to compute the transition probabilities between any two locations depending on the destination and time, which implicitly defines the distribution of all paths between the source and the destination at a given time. Finally, a realistic path is generated by sampling from this distribution with a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method.
2. Our composite generative model can be trained with differentially private gradient descent [1] on sensitive location data, and, therefore, can be used to synthesize the training data with formally proven privacy guarantees. Such synthetic training data can be shared for any purposes without violating individuals' privacy.
3. We evaluate our model on three real-life public mobility datasets, and demonstrate that the generated private synthetic data has higher utility compared to previous works.

3.1 Related work

A prominent line of anonymization research uses the notion of Differential Privacy [23] which gives a privacy guarantee based on rigorous mathematical proofs. Some proposals based on synthetic data generation via machine learning, i.e., modeling the dataset through the underlying distributions of generating variables, do apply Differential Privacy specifically for location data [17, 47], but with significant shortcomings. He et al.[47] (DPT) discretize raw GPS trajectories using hierarchical reference systems to capture individual movements at different speeds. They then propose an adaptive mechanism to select a small set of reference systems to construct prefix tree counts. Lastly, a direction-weighted sampling is applied to improve utility.

Chen et al. designed Ngram [17], a variable-length n-gram model that makes use of an exploration tree structure and Markovian assumptions, with Differential Privacy. Gursoy et al. [42] designed AdaTrace, a generative model with a four-phase synthesis

process consisting of feature extraction, synopsis learning, differentially private noise injection and synthetic trace generation. Additionally, they provided defense against three ad-hoc privacy attacks. Bindschaedler and Shokri [11] (SGLT) enforce plausible deniability to generate privacy-preserving synthetic traces. SGLT first recommends trace similarity and intersection functions that map a synthetic trace to an original one under similarity and intersection constraints. Then, it generates one synthetic trace using one real trace as its seed. If the synthetic trace satisfies plausible deniability, i.e., there exist k other real traces that can be mapped to the synthetic trace, then it preserves the privacy of the seed trace. DPT and Ngram generate synthetic traces as random walks that do not incorporate destinations. However, a realistic trace heavily depends on the destination, and humans rarely visit a location following a *“let’s go to a place where people usually go from here”* policy. In addition, a random walk can possibly generate synthetic traces with unrealistic length (see details in Section 3.4). Moreover, time-of-day is also left out from the models (Ngram, DPT, AdaTrace); clearly, this reduces the descriptive power of the generative model as human mobility does show strong time-of-day patterns [39]. In fact, time-of-day even influences trip destinations. (Just consider how your destination varies from 8am to 8pm.) Simply dropping the timestamps averages out the visit frequencies between night and day, morning and afternoon etc. SGLT applies large bins in order to incorporate time (morning, afternoon, evening and night). However, SGLT is mainly designed for CDR (Call Detail Record) datasets, and it utilizes the peculiarities of the implied mobility patterns, such as semantic similarity (SGLT) between locations. This approach can hardly generate valuable synthetic data when it comes to short term, dense movements, such as GPS trajectories of vehicles between start and end locations. Borrowing the example from [11], consider Alice and Bob spending all day at their respective work locations w_A and w_B , and all night at their respective home locations h_A and h_B . Obviously, their mobility models are semantically very similar, although it might be the case that $h_A \neq h_B$ and $w_A \neq w_B$. In this example, the best semantic mapping between locations will be $w_A \leftrightarrow w_B$ and $h_A \leftrightarrow h_B$. This example clearly introduces the type of mobility traces generated by this model. In our experiments, we applied datasets of vehicle trajectories where the above illustrated semantic similarity is not applicable at all times. Furthermore, in CDR-like data, we can mostly observe the locations where people reside for longer periods (such as work and home), while DP-Loc models individuals’ movements from one of these locations to another, where the turns and stops depend on the hour of the day (e.g., owing to traffic jams). For example, oftentimes we take a different route from home to work depending on the traffic conditions. More formally, in the case of CDR (or similar) datasets, the transition probabilities between locations are closer to uniform; however, when we increase the

sampling rate of locations along a route, this does not hold anymore (particularly when we also condition on time and destination), thus allowing us to build better models. Our model is best suited for trips that have a start and destination that can be fit in the same time-slot. For different datasets different time granularity can be used based on the underlying application. However, for CDR-like data, we suggest two possible alterations: (1) setting one time-slot to one day, or (2) remove all time information. The evaluation of these scenarios go beyond the scope of this work, hence we leave them for future research.

Ngram, DPT and AdaTrace apply the Laplace mechanism to preserve Differential Privacy, where the noise is added to the Markovian probabilities. In contrast to these, we apply the Moments Accountant [1] method with the Gaussian mechanism that utilizes an advanced composition theorem by taking into account the exact noise distribution. Finally, SGLT has been shown [42] to be very slow, while DPT requires large computational power (256GB RAM and 48 cores for 50,000 traces, whereas we generate 400,000 traces), thus these models are not scalable for large datasets.

Most privacy-preserving training algorithms for neural networks are based on modifying the gradient information generated during backpropagation. The modification involves clipping the gradients (to bound the influence of any single record on the released model parameters) and adding calibrated random noise [1, 15]. Some works propose to use generative adversarial networks (GANs) [60] or mixture models [3] to directly generate privacy-preserving synthetic data. Differentially Private GAN [74, 79, 70] has been applied to generate image and Electronic Health Record data. The approach in [34] aims to generate time series with LSTM (Long-Short Term Memory Networks) and GAN (Generative Adversarial Networks) with DP guarantees, as well as multi-variate tabular data. GS-WGAN [16] uses gradient-sanitized Wasserstein GAN to generate synthetic data and has also been demonstrated on image data. Another DP-GAN architecture was proposed in [8] to release patient-level clinical trial data with Differential Privacy. All these techniques use some variant of DP-SGD (Differentially Private Stochastic Gradient Descent) [1] for training the discriminator of GAN. By contrast, PATE-GAN [52] was proposed to generate synthetic multi-variate tabular data using PATE [59]. Nonetheless, none of these generative models are specific to location data generation.

3.2 Preliminaries

3.2.1 Location Data

In general, location data is geographical information about a specific object's whereabouts associated to a time identifier. Formally, let $\mathbf{L} = \{L_1, L_2, \dots, L_{|\mathbf{L}|}\}$ be the universe of locations, where $|\mathbf{L}|$ is the size of the universe. We assume that the whole universe is represented as a grid, and each location corresponds to a cell in the grid. Each record in a location database is a sequence of timestamped location visits drawn from the universe. Specifically, a sequence S of length $|S|$ is an ordered list of items $S = (L_{\ell_1}, t_1) \rightarrow (L_{\ell_2}, t_2) \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow (L_{\ell_{|S|}}, t_{|S|})$, where $\forall 1 \leq i \leq |S|, L_{\ell_i} \in \mathbf{L}$. A location may occur multiple times in S . A location database D is composed of a multiset of sequences $D = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_{|D|}\}$, where $|D| = N$ denotes the number of traces in D .

3.2.2 Differential Privacy

Differential Privacy [25] (DP) ensures that the outcome of any computation on a database is insensitive to the change of a single record. It follows that any information that can be learned from the database with a record can also be learned from the one without that particular record. In our case, DP guarantees that our generative model is not affected by any single original trace beyond the privacy budget measured by ϵ and δ , which can be computed as follows.

Definition 3.2.1 ((ϵ, δ) -Differential Privacy [24]). *A privacy mechanism \mathcal{M} gives (ϵ, δ) -Differential Privacy if for any database D_1 and D_2 differing on at most one record and for any subset of outputs $S \subseteq \text{Range}(\mathcal{M})$:*

$$\Pr[\mathcal{M}(D_1) \in S] \leq e^\epsilon \Pr[\mathcal{M}(D_2) \in S] + \delta$$

Intuitively, a privacy mechanism \mathcal{M} satisfying Definition 3.2.1 does not release any information that is specific to any single record in dataset D up to ϵ and δ , where δ is preferably smaller than $1/|D|$ [24].

A fundamental concept for achieving Differential Privacy is the global sensitivity of a function [25]:

Definition 3.2.2 (Global L_p -sensitivity [26]). For any function $f : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, the L_p -sensitivity of f is $\Delta f = \max_{D_1, D_2} \|f(D_1) - f(D_2)\|_p$ for all D_1, D_2 differing in at most one record, where $\|\cdot\|_p$ denotes the L_p -norm.

Differential Privacy maintains composition; the privacy guarantee of the k -fold adaptive composition of any mechanism can be computed using the moments accountant method [1]. i.e., if each of the mechanisms $\mathcal{M}_1, \dots, \mathcal{M}_k$ is (ϵ, δ) -DP, then their k -fold adaptive composition is $(k\epsilon, k\delta)$ -DP. However, a tighter upper bound can be derived from advanced composition theorems such as in [13]. The moments accountant generalizes the regular approach of keeping track of (ϵ, δ) using an advanced composition theorem by taking into account the exact noise distribution. In order to present the bounds given by the moments accountant, we first introduce the log of the moment generating function and the notion of privacy loss:

Definition 3.2.3 (Privacy loss [1]). Let \mathcal{M} be a privacy mechanism which assigns a value $O \in \text{Range}(\mathcal{M})$ to a dataset D . The privacy loss of \mathcal{M} with datasets D_1 and D_2 and auxiliary input aux at output O is a random variable:

$$\mathcal{L}(O; D_1, D_2, \mathcal{M}, aux) = \log \frac{P[\mathcal{M}(D_1, aux) = O]}{P[\mathcal{M}(D_2, aux) = O]}$$

where the probability is taken on the randomness of \mathcal{M} .

Intuitively, the privacy loss, as a random variable, describes the value of ϵ for a specific output O , and (ϵ, δ) -DP guarantees that every output of algorithm \mathcal{M} is almost equally likely (up to ϵ) on datasets differing in a single record except with probability at most δ , preferably smaller than $1/|D|$.

Definition 3.2.4. (Log of the Moment Generating Function) For a given mechanism \mathcal{M} , the log of the moment generating function evaluated at λ is: $\alpha_{\mathcal{M}}(\lambda; aux, D_1, D_2) = \log \mathbb{E}_{O \sim \mathcal{M}(D_1, aux)}[\exp(\lambda \mathcal{L}(O; D_1, D_2, \mathcal{M}, aux))]$.

Theorem 3.2.1. (Moments Accountant [1]) Let $\alpha_{\mathcal{M}}(\lambda) = \max_{aux, D_1, D_2} \alpha_{\mathcal{M}}(\lambda; aux, D_1, D_2)$ be defined as above. Let $\mathcal{M}_{1:k}$ be the k -fold adaptive composition of $\mathcal{M}_1, \dots, \mathcal{M}_k$. Then:

1. *Composability:* $\alpha_{\mathcal{M}_{1:k}}(\lambda) \leq \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_{\mathcal{M}_i}(\lambda)$
2. *Tail bound:* For any $\epsilon > 0$, the mechanism $\mathcal{M}_{1:k}$ is (ϵ, δ) -differentially private for $\delta = \min_{\lambda} \exp(\alpha_{\mathcal{M}_{1:k}}(\lambda) - \lambda\epsilon)$.

The *Gaussian Mechanism* [26] consists of adding Gaussian noise to the true output of a function. In particular, for any function $f : D \rightarrow R^n$, the Gaussian mechanism is defined as adding i.i.d. Gaussian noise with variance $(\Delta_2 f \cdot \sigma)$ and zero mean to each coordinate value of $f(D)$. In fact, the Gaussian mechanism draws vector values from a multivariate isotropic Gaussian distribution which is described by random variable $\mathcal{G}(f(D), \Delta_2 f \cdot \sigma \mathbf{I}_n)$.

3.3 Model

3.3.1 Overview

Our goal is to generate private synthetic location traces. In particular, having a location dataset D with a multiset of trajectories, our goal is to build a generative model which approximates the true generator distribution of D , where every trace in D is a sample from this distribution. The model is built using the privacy-sensitive data D , and, hence, the training process of this model must guarantee Differential Privacy for any user/trace in D . Due to the large complexity of this model, we decompose it into four main parts as follows:

1. **Dimensionality reduction:** We identify the K most frequently visited cells on the map and work only with these locations afterwards by projecting all trajectories to these cells.
2. **Trace Initialization:** A generative model, called *Trace Initializer (TI)*, learns the underlying joint distribution of the starting and ending locations and time variable of all trajectories, i.e., their very first (source) and very last (destination) location visits along with the single timestamp of the whole trace.
3. **Transition Probability Generation:** A classification model, called *Transition Probability Generator (TPG)*, learns the transition probability distribution between any two consecutive locations, i.e., it outputs the probability distribution for the next hop in a trace, conditioned on the current location, the destination and time. Both of these models are trained with Differential Privacy guarantees on a potentially sensitive training dataset.
4. **Trace Generation:** Sampling a source L_{src} and destination L_{dst} along with the time t from the output distribution of TI, and using the transition probabilities between any locations generated by TPG, the trace generator (TG) non-deterministically reconstructs a trace between source L_{src} and destination L_{dst} at time t combining Dijkstra’s shortest path and the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm.

Algorithm 1 Differentially Private Synthetic Trace Generator (DP-Loc)

Input: Private Dataset D

Dimensionality reduction:

Choose K most frequent locations TOP- K : $L_{\ell_1}, \dots, L_{\ell_K}, \forall L_{\ell_i} \in \mathbf{L}$ with Gaussian Mechanism

Project each trace $p \in D$ to TOP- K

Model construction:

Train the Trace Initialization Model TI_{θ_1} on D with DP-SGD [1]

Train the Transition Probability Generation Model TPG_{θ_2} on D with DP-SGD [1]

Trace Reconstruction:

for $i \in [1, \dots, |D|]$ **do**

 Sample $(L_{src}, L_{dst}, t) \sim TI_{\theta_1}$

 Build a routing graph

$G(V, E), V = \mathbf{L}$ and $weight((L_x, L_y)) = -\log TPG_{\theta_2}[L_y|t, L_x, L_{dst}]$, where $(L_x, L_y) \in E$

 Find the path p between L_{src} and L_{dst} with the minimal total weight in G

for $m \in [1, \dots, 10]$ **do**

 Run Metropolis-Hastings on p : $p = MH(p)$

end

 Generate repetitions in the sampled path $s = (L_{\ell_1}, \dots, L_{\ell_n})$:

for $L_{\ell_j} \in s$ **do**

$\eta \sim Geom(1 - TPG_{\theta_2}[L_{\ell_j}|t, L_{\ell_{j-1}}, L_{\ell_n}])$ $s' = (L_{\ell_1}, \dots, L_{\ell_{j-1}}, \underbrace{L_{\ell_j}, \dots, L_{\ell_j}}_{\eta \text{ times}}, L_{\ell_{j+1}}, \dots, L_{\ell_n})$

end

$D' = D' \cup \{(s', t)\}$

end

Output: Synthetic dataset D'

As this process only uses the output of TI and TPG, and some public information about locations, the whole generation process becomes differentially private as the first two are already differentially private.

Assumptions: Time is divided into equally sized slots which are sufficiently large to include whole trajectories. Each trace is assigned to a single time slot t , and all location visits of a trace take place within this slot t .

3.3.2 Model Description

In the remainder of this section, we describe our approach called DP-Loc (Differentially Private Synthetic Trace Generator) in more details that is also summarized in Alg. 1.

Dimensionality reduction

We project all locations of every trace to the K most frequently visited locations (cells) on the map called as TOP- K locations. In particular, each location is mapped to the closest TOP- K location if there is any within a distance of 1000m. Otherwise, the whole

trace is dropped. The value K refers to the number of most frequently visited cells where 95% of all visits occur; thus, it differs among datasets, and must be chosen in a differentially private fashion (see Section 3.4.6 and Section 3.3.3). (We made an exception and lowered the threshold percentage in case of GeoLife-250 dataset to 80% because of the low amount of datapoints in many cells. The same preprocessing was done for Ngram and AdaTrace as well.) The purpose of this dimensionality reduction is to increase model accuracy and also the speed of training. Indeed, if there are many cells on the map, the number of visits per cell typically has a power-law distribution: most cells are never or rarely visited. Using all grid cells would largely increase model complexity and hence training time. Moreover, it also degrades model quality due to the larger perturbation needed by DP (see Section 3.3.3). On the other hand, dimensionality reduction helps the model preserve large-scale mobility patterns more accurately (with high support) at the expense of losing fine-grained patterns (with low support). This trade-off can be dynamically chosen per application; we believe that retaining 95% of all visits provides reasonably high fidelity.

Trace Initialization (TI)

In order to sample a starting location $L_{src} \in \mathbf{L}$, a destination $L_{dst} \in \mathbf{L}$ and time $t \in \mathbf{T}$ for a synthetic trace, we build a differentially private Variational Autoencoder (VAE) (see Figure 3.1a for illustration) that is capable of approximating the joint probability distribution $Pr(L_{src}, L_{dst}, t)$. The model parameters θ_1 are learnt from a sensitive location dataset D , and hence training is performed with DP-SGD [1] (see Section 3.3.3 for details).

The output of TI_{θ_1} is a 3-dimensional vector $[L_{src}, L_{dst}, t]$ (recall that each trace has a single timestamp in our model). Notice that learning this distribution privately is challenging due to its high dimensionality; the domain of the joint probability distribution is $|\mathbf{L}| \times |\mathbf{L}| \times |\mathbf{T}|$, where $|\mathbf{T}|$ is the number of all possible time slots.

We one-hot encode the input, thus it has a dimension of $2 \times |\mathbf{L}| + 24$, where the size of $|\mathbf{L}|$ depends on the coarseness of the grid, and 24 is the number of hours in a day. Our encoder has two hidden *dense* layers (100, 100) with ReLU and linear activation functions, respectively. The encoder outputs the parameters of the learned normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$; values drawn from this distribution by the decoder comprise the latent vectors of size 50. The decoder has to transform this latent variable to an actual sample. The decoder has only 1 hidden layer with size 100 and with ReLU activation. Finally, there are three parallel output layers with softmax activation, corresponding to a single output variable (location, destination, time). VAEs have their own specific loss functions; we applied the original one from [21].

Remarks

We have experimented with different input representations for the VAE, such as projecting the input to a Hilbert curve or simply using coordinates of the cells. This way our first approach was a regression model and not classification. However, these preliminary results did not bring good results. Later, by also applying our dimensionality reduction we turned to classification (thus one-hot encoding), this led to smaller loss on the VAE and better values overall with our metrics. We hypothesize that this improvement is due to the change in feature space, an input neuron is dedicated to a single feature and therefore higher level neurons can easily learn dependence between features. Nonetheless, this question is highly complex, and we leave it to future work.

(a) Trace Initialization model

(b) Transition Probability Generator model

Figure 3.1: The neural network architectures used in DP-Loc

Transition Probability Generation (TPG)

Our classifier TPG_{θ_2} is a feed forward network (FFN) endowed with word embedding. It is illustrated in Figure 3.1b. It approximates the true transition distribution $Pr[L_x \rightarrow$

$L_y|t, L_{dst}]$ for any frequent (see details below) location L_x and L_y for every possible time slot $t \in \mathbf{T}$ and destination $L_{dst} \in \mathbf{L}$. That is, the probability that an individual at location L_x moves to location L_y towards destination L_{dst} at time t .

The input is (L_c, L_{dst}, t) (current location, destination, time), and the output is the probability distribution on the next hop. The two location coordinates of the input vector are fed into an embedding layer where they are embedded separately into the same 50-dimensional vector space⁴. Next, we concatenate these vectors with the time coordinate, resulting in a 101-dimensional vector. The next dense layer has a size of 200 with ReLU activation, and the output layer has softmax. We trained the network with *sparse categorical cross-entropy* and the *SGD* optimizer. As only the K most frequently visited cells are considered, the number of output classes is also K . We use DP-SGD [1] to train TPG and therefore the released model parameters θ_2 are differentially private (see Section 3.3.3 for details). Besides the current time and destination, the prediction of the next location depends only on the current location and not on the earlier location visits. That is, when the next location is predicted, we do not take into account how the current location is reached. This is not a far-fetched simplification; several studies have shown that 1 or at most 2-order Markov chains provide a sufficiently accurate estimation of the next location visit [37].

Remarks

The choice of an embedding layer, and an FFN instead of a recurrent neural network (such as LSTM) deserves more explanation. As locations exhibit similar characteristics to words, we can rely on the distributional hypothesis⁵. In case of locations, this means that if they follow each other in a given trace, then they are also close in the geographical space, and, therefore, will have similar representations in the embedded space. This implies that the model can automatically learn which locations are geographically close to each other.

Although LSTM has an implicit capability to handle temporal and sequential data, its differentially private training with SGD takes approximately 6-8 times longer than without Differential Privacy. However, training simple feed forward networks is considerably faster, almost as fast as the non-private model. Furthermore, our FFN has less parameters than the simplest but still well-performing LSTM, and having less parameters results in lower noise injection, and thus, higher utility. Our solution has an accuracy only 1-2% less than the LSTM layer on the considered datasets.

⁴The embedding layer is part of the network, thus trained together with the rest of the layers.

⁵Words that co-occur in the same contexts tend to have similar meanings

Trace Generation (TG)

When a trace is generated, we first sample a pair of source L_{src} and destination L_{dst} locations along with the time slot t from the output distribution of TI_{θ_1} . Then, a weighted directed routing graph $G(V, E)$ is built, where the edge weights are the transition probabilities between any two location points generated by TPG_{θ_2} (i.e., V is composed of locations in TOP-K, and $weight((L_x, L_y)) = -\log Pr[L_x \rightarrow L_y|t, L_{dst}]$ for any $(L_x, L_y) \in E$, that is the negative logarithm of the transition probability from L_x to L_y conditioned on destination D and time t). Note that G is complete and specific to a given destination L_{dst} and time slot t , hence different graphs are constructed for trajectories differing in their destination or time. The routing graph defines a distribution of paths between any location and destination L_{dst} at time t , and our task is to draw a path from this distribution in order to generate a trace.

To do so, the most probable trace is first constructed from graph G by applying Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm, and then the Metropolis-Hastings MCMC algorithm to the resulting shortest path, thus we generate one of the most probable paths between L_{src} and L_{dst} . As $-\log TPG_{\theta_2}[L_y|t, L_x, L_{dst}]$ is always non-negative, Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm finds the path with the minimum total weight between two vertices, which is equivalent to the most probable path between L_{src} and L_{dst} at time t in our case. Indeed, let P denote the set of all paths between L_{src} and L_{dst} . Then, the probability of the most probable path between L_{src} and L_{dst} is

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_{p \in P} \sum_{(L_x \rightarrow L_y) \in p} -\log(TPG_{\theta_2}[L_y|t, L_x, L_{dst}]) \\
&= \min_{p \in P} -\log\left(\prod_{(L_x \rightarrow L_y) \in p} TPG_{\theta_2}[L_y|t, L_x, L_{dst}]\right) \\
&\approx \min_{p \in P} -\log\left(\prod_{(L_x \rightarrow L_y) \in p} Pr[L_x \rightarrow L_y|t, L_{dst}]\right) \\
&= \max_{p \in P} \prod_{(L_x \rightarrow L_y) \in p} Pr[L_x \rightarrow L_y|t, L_{dst}]
\end{aligned}$$

due to the monotonicity property of the logarithm.

This path finding algorithm is deterministic on its own, however this would not account for real life scenarios. Two vehicles can take different routes between identical starting and ending locations (depending on random environmental factors such as traffic, weather, road blocks, etc.). Therefore, we introduce randomness into our trace generation by applying the *Metropolis-Hastings algorithm* (MH) to the shortest path. Specifically, we have a target stationary distribution over all paths, where the probability of a path is computed as above from the routing graph. Sampling directly from this distribution is hard due to its finite but exponentially large domain, therefore, we rely on MCMC meth-

Algorithm 2 Metropolis-Hastings Algorithm for TG

Input: Most probable path $p = (L_{src} = L_{\ell_1}, L_{\ell_2}, \dots, L_{\ell_n} = L_{dst})$

Choose uniformly random node $L_{\ell_i} \sim U(p \setminus \{L_{\ell_1}, L_{\ell_n}\})$

Choose uniformly random neighbor $L_{\ell_i}^n$ of L_{ℓ_i}

Candidate path $p_c = (L_{\ell_1}, \dots, L_{\ell_{i-1}}, L_{\ell_i}^n, L_{\ell_{i+1}}, \dots, L_{\ell_n})$

Let $\gamma = \frac{\prod_{(L_x \rightarrow L_y) \in p_c} TPG_{\theta_2}[L_y|t, L_x, L_{dst}]}{\prod_{(L_x \rightarrow L_y) \in p} TPG_{\theta_2}[L_y|t, L_x, L_{dst}]}$

$p = \begin{cases} p_c & \text{with probability } \min(1, \gamma) \\ p & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Output: p

ods. Our MH algorithm applied to shortest paths is described in Algorithm 2. Markov chain theory says that we need multiple state transitions to have a “good enough” sample (that comes from a distribution close enough to the target), we perform 10 transitions. We set this value based on our *Route Distribution metric* (see Section 3.4.3) that measures the distance between original and synthetic routes taken between source-destination pairs. Our experiments in Section 3.4 show that 10 iterations are sufficient for larger datasets, however, smaller databases benefit from 100 and even 150 iterations.

The final step in our TG algorithm is *looping*, where we aim to approximate the time a vehicle stays in one cell, that is, the number of repetitions of a single location in a trace. Looping allows to capture some traffic patterns more faithfully such as rush hours or traffic jams. We model this by generating the repetition number η of a location L_x from a geometric distribution $\eta \sim Geom(1 - TPG_{\theta_2}[L_x|t, L_x, L_{dst}])$, where $TPG_{\theta_2}[L_x|t, L_x, L_{dst}]$ is the probability output of TPG for staying at location L_x .

Remarks

Feeding the destination and time as an input to our transition probability generator enhances model accuracy by a large margin (in certain cases with more than 20%). The rationale behind this is that the probability of the next-hop location is heavily influenced by the direction of movement, i.e., the specific destination where the individual is heading for. Similarly, time also impacts the direction of movement towards a specific destination, especially in vehicular transport, where the route of a vehicle is largely influenced by the traffic, i.e., ultimately time dependent. This is in sharp contrast to earlier works [17] which solely used the last visited locations to predict the next location of a trace.

3.3.3 Privacy Analysis

In this section, we quantify the privacy guarantee of DP-Loc by using the moments accountant described in Section 3.2.2. Recall that we use the Gaussian Mechanism to provide DP for the dimensionality reduction (Section 3.3.2), and DP-SGD [1] for TI

(Section 3.3.2) and TPG (Section 3.3.2). DP-Loc is the adaptive composition of these three mechanisms plus the trace generation (TG) described in Section 3.3.2.

Dimensionality reduction

To select the most frequent K (top- K) cells, we employ the Gaussian mechanism (see Section 3.2.2) and add i.i.d Gaussian noise $\mathcal{G}(L_{max}\sigma_K)$ to the visit counts of *all* cells, where L_{max} is an upper bound on the trace length, and return the cells as top- K which have the K largest noisy counts. Both K and L are chosen based on the threshold where 95% of the visits is included in our calculations.

TI and TPG models

To train the TI and the TPG models, we use the Differentially Private Stochastic Gradient Descent (DP-SGD) by Abadi et al. [1]. This method is independent of the chosen loss function and model, and it adds noise to the clipped gradients. In particular, the gradients of all model parameters in every model update are clipped to have a bounded L_2 -norm with value C , and then Gaussian noise with variance $C_{TI}^2\sigma_{TI}^2$ (for TI) and $C_{TPG}^2\sigma_{TPG}^2$ (for TPG) is added to the clipped gradients before updating the parameters. The output of DP-SGD are the parameters θ_1 and θ_2 of TI and TPG, respectively. The sampling probability q in DP-SGD is calculated as follows. Our aim is to provide user-level (or in our case trace-level) Differential Privacy. However, recall that trajectories have different lengths, and we divided them into 1-grams: thus there are variable number of training examples belonging to a single trace for TPG. In the case of our TI model, we only have one sample per trace, thus the sampling probability of a single trace here is at most $|B|/|D|$, where $|D|$ is the total number of trajectories and $|B|$ is the size of batch B . However, for TPG, a single trace can have multiple samples, therefore, we sample batches differently. We first sample a trace from the dataset uniformly at random, and then a 2-gram out of this trace also uniformly at random. We repeat this experiment until a batch B of grams (training samples for TPG) is collected. This sampling mechanism ensures that any trace is equally probable to participate in an update (batch), and hence the sampling probability becomes $q = \frac{|B|}{|D|}$.

Trace Generation (TG)

The trace generation uses only the differentially private models TI_{θ_1} and TPG_{θ_2} as input, and does not access private data. Therefore, the generated traces are also differentially private due to the post-processing property of DP.

Let $\eta_0(x|\xi) = \text{pdf}_{\mathcal{G}(0,\xi)}(x)$ and $\eta_1(x|\xi) = (1 - q)\text{pdf}_{\mathcal{G}(0,\xi)}(x) + q\text{pdf}_{\mathcal{G}(1,\xi)}(x)$ where q is the sampling probability of a single trace in a single round. Let

$$\alpha_K(\lambda) = (\lambda^2 + \lambda)/4\sigma_K^2 \quad (3.1)$$

$$\alpha_{TI}(\lambda) = \log \max(E_1(\lambda, \sigma_{TI}), E_2(\lambda, \sigma_{TI})) \quad (3.2)$$

$$\alpha_{TPG}(\lambda) = \log \max(E_1(\lambda, \sigma_{TPG}), E_2(\lambda, \sigma_{TPG})) \quad (3.3)$$

where $E_1(\lambda, \xi) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} \eta_0(x|\xi) \cdot \left(\frac{\eta_0(x|\xi)}{\eta_1(x|\xi)}\right)^\lambda dx$, $E_2(\lambda, \xi) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} \eta_1(x|\xi) \cdot \left(\frac{\eta_1(x|\xi)}{\eta_0(x|\xi)}\right)^\lambda dx$, and $\alpha_K(\lambda)$, $\alpha_{TI}(\lambda)$, $\alpha_{TPG}(\lambda)$ are the log moments (see Definition 3.2.4) of the TOP-K identification, TI, and TPG, respectively. $\alpha_K(\lambda)$ in Eq. (3.1) follows from Lemma 1 in [3].

Theorem 3.3.1 (Privacy of DP-Loc). *Let e_{TI} and e_{TPG} denote the number of epochs for TI and TPG, and $|B|/|D|$ is the number of SGD iterations per epoch. DP-Loc is (ϵ, δ) -DP, where*

$$\epsilon = \min_{\lambda} \frac{1}{\lambda} \left(\alpha_K(\lambda) + \frac{|B|}{|D|} e_{TI} \alpha_{TI}(\lambda) + \frac{|B|}{|D|} e_{TPG} \alpha_{TPG}(\lambda) - \log(\delta) \right)$$

Proof. Let $\alpha_{DPLoc}(\lambda)$ denote the log moment DP-Loc in Alg. 1. It follows from the second part of Theorem 3.2.1 that $\epsilon = \min_{\lambda} \frac{1}{\lambda} (\alpha_{DPLoc}(\lambda) - \log \delta)$. Since dimensionality reduction is only applied once at the very beginning of DP-Loc, and there are $\frac{|B|}{|D|} e_{TI}$ SGD iterations in TI and $\frac{|B|}{|D|} e_{TPG}$ SGD iterations in TPG in total, it also follows from the first part of Theorem 3.2.1 that $\alpha_{DPLoc}(\lambda) \leq \alpha_K(\lambda) + \frac{|B|}{|D|} e_{TI} \alpha_{TI}(\lambda) + \frac{|B|}{|D|} e_{TPG} \alpha_{TPG}(\lambda)$ which concludes the proof. \square

Given a fixed value of δ , ϵ is computed numerically as in [1].

Note on Membership Inference Attacks

It is a common practice nowadays to test models with membership attacks, i.e. when an adversary queries a trained machine learning model to predict whether or not a particular example was contained in the model’s training dataset. This way an attacker could test samples and differentiate between synthetic and real ones. However, the loss-thresholding baseline membership attack from [66] has an average accuracy of 59%, and does not tell us anything about worst case attacks. This means that this attack does not confidently infer membership on any member of the training set. However, in a recent work of Carlini et al. [14] the authors argue that attacks should be evaluated by computing their true-positive rate at low (e.g., $\leq 0.1\%$) false-positive rates. The devised attack uses a Likelihood-ratio Test between two hypotheses (the sample was in or out of the

training set) and gives better results than previous works. Moreover, the authors give an other attack where they can tell with high confidence about outliers’ membership. However, Differential Privacy inherently bounds the success of any membership inference attack, first of all because it gives worst case guarantees and also the true-positive and false-positive ratio (as given by the authors as good metric) is what Differential Privacy bounds. Consequently, the accuracy of a membership inference attack cannot be better than the bound set with Differential Privacy, thus such membership inference attacks can be used for auditing differentially private mechanisms. If the attack shows different results that has been stated before (such as higher ϵ values), the auditor can tell that there must be a miscalculation or implementation error in the audited mechanism.

3.4 Experimental evaluation

In this section, we empirically evaluate DP-Loc on three publicly available datasets, where two contain the GPS trajectories of different taxi trips from San Francisco [61] and Porto [57], and one has miscellaneous trajectories (e.g., walking, driving, public transport, cycling) (mostly) from Beijing, China (*GeoLife* dataset [83, 80, 82]). We show that the synthetic trajectories generated by our model are close to the original trajectories according to four different utility metrics, and apply a fifth utility metric to demonstrate the usefulness of the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm. The architecture described in Section 3.3.2 is fixed for all datasets. Although it has been shown that the optimization of hyperparameters (including the architecture of DP-Loc) is possible with DP guarantees [1, 41], yet this requires a larger privacy budget. For simplicity and owing to the similarity of the three datasets evaluated, we do not apply this technique here.

3.4.1 Data

San Francisco taxi

The original San Francisco (SF) taxi dataset contains a set of GPS trajectories with timestamps recorded by 536 taxis. They were collected over 30 days in the San Francisco Bay Area of the USA in 2009. The trajectories cover the region of San Francisco within the bounding box of (37.6017N, 122.5158W) and (37.8112N, 122.3527W) – approximately 340 km². The original sampling rate of these trajectories is roughly 1 per minute. We used all the 276744 trajectories from the SF dataset.

Porto taxi

The original Porto dataset contains 1.7 million GPS trajectories with timestamps of 441 taxis. This dataset was acquired in the metropolitan area of Porto, Portugal, over a period of nine months in 2012. The sampling rate varies, but it is approximately 1 per 15 seconds. We considered taxi trips only within a bounding box of (41.00456N, -8.7368W) and (41.2728N, -8.4412W) around the city, with a size of approximately 600 km². We used a random sub-sample containing 450,000 trips for our evaluation.

GeoLife

The original GeoLife dataset is a collection of 17,621 daily trajectories by 182 users in a period of over five years (from April 2007 to August 2012). 91.5% of the trajectories are logged in a dense representation, e.g., every 1-5 seconds or every 5-10 meters per point. The GeoLife dataset includes a wide range of outdoor user movements, including commuting, entertainment and sports activities, such as shopping, sightseeing, dining, hiking, and cycling. The majority of the data was generated in Beijing, China, where we set our bounding box of (39.75N, 116.2W) and (40.1N, 116.55W) of approximately 580 km², and considered the traces within this region only. Note that Porto and GeoLife cover approximately the same area size, however, the Porto bounding box also contains its uptown area while GeoLife does not. In other words, the whole Beijing area is populated uniformly almost everywhere with approximately one seventh in available data points of the Porto dataset. Moreover, since the dataset contains continuous recordings of people's daily traces with multiple stationary locations, we cut these traces along their stationary locations and replace the original trace with its sub-traces in the dataset. More precisely, if an individual stayed at one location for a long time (more than 15 minutes), then the location is regarded as stationary and we terminated the given trace and initialized a new one with the current cell as new starting point. The justification behind such slicing is twofold. First, we intend to model and release only the mobility patterns of people which is the main focus of most practical applications (such as traffic optimization). Second, the original GeoLife dataset is small in terms of both individuals and traces; with the help of trace slicing we obtained 59,907 traces. Note that (strictly speaking) DP-Loc provides DP guarantees only to individual sub-traces in this case; however, we embrace this limitation on two accounts: i) we could not obtain a larger suitable third dataset, ii) the limited number of users in the original GeoLife dataset would result in a low utility irrespective of the actual DP-based privacy-preserving mechanism applied. *Remarks* Regarding the taxi datasets our objective is to preserve the privacy of passengers and not

taxi drivers, and hence a trace (sequence) is composed of the recorded location visits of a single taxi trip.

3.4.2 Data Preprocessing

We consider two grids with different cell size. The smaller grid consists of cells with size of $250 \times 250\text{m}^2$, and the larger one with cells of size $500 \times 500\text{m}^2$. We have found that these two sizes are small enough to capture the movement of an individual, and also large enough to enable neural networks to learn the underlying distribution with sufficient accuracy and low computational cost (see the the complexity analysis in Subsection 3.4.6). Although, in a real-life scenario, a given application can change these sizes, we believe that most practical use-cases would not divert very much from these values. Each GPS location point is assigned to its covering cell. Therefore, every trace (taxi trip) is composed of the sequence of location visits, each containing a pair of cell and the time of the visit. All traces with velocity larger than 150 km/h (calculated between two GPS points) or being out of the bounding box are dropped. Since the sampling rate was not constant in the database, we applied two transformations to make it more regular; (1) cell visits are aggregated in time by 60 seconds keeping the cell that was the most frequent in the trace during this time frame, and (2) when there were gaps shorter than 5 minutes without any location visits, these missing visits are approximated by linear interpolation. We select the K cells that contain at least 95% of all visits in a privacy-preserving manner and we map each point to the closest top- K cell, if there is any within 1000m. We drop traces with locations that cannot be assigned to a top- K cell. Finally, if the resulting trace had only a single visit, it is dropped. All traces are truncated to length L_{max} . Since DP adds noise to the cell counts, the values of K and L can change between runs; however, larger datasets are not prone to this instability. To illustrate this, we generated the values of K and L 5 times and included their average in Table 3.1. The standard deviation for Porto and SF were 0, however, for GeoLife it was 20 for the K values; the L values were stable in all cases. The data loss caused by top- K filtering was 3 – 5% for all datasets. Less than 1% of traces were dropped by the other filters.

After cleaning and smoothing the data, the timestamps are further aggregated by assigning only the hour of the day, when the dominant part of the taxi trace was present, to all visits of a single trace. For example, if a trace started at 17:58, and ended at 18:10 with 12 visits altogether, we assigned the 18th hour of the day to every cell visit of the trace (including those which happened before 18:00). As our aim is only to demonstrate the feasibility of our approach, this simplification is introduced in order to decrease the size of the input and output space making training faster and the models less complex.

Dataset	$ D $	$topK$	$\max t $	$\text{avg} t $	$\text{std.dev} t $	$\text{mode} t $
SF-250	431,222	550	19	10.54	6.67	7
SF-500	431,222	179	19	10.46	6.17	7
Porto-250	450,000	490	24	11.63	7.53	9
Porto-500	450,000	211	24	11.52	8.64	9
GeoLife-250	59,907	406	14	13.91	11.38	10
GeoLife-500	59,907	503	22	13.86	11.38	10

Table 3.1: The preprocessed datasets used in our experiments: SF-250, Porto-250, GeoLife-250 (with a cell size of $250m^2$) and SF-500, Porto-500, GeoLife-500 (with a cell size of $500m^2$). Trace length $|t|$ is for traces $t \in D$.

Finally, we created 2-grams from the traces, i.e., we grouped every two consecutive data points together to create a single training sample for our TPG model, where the first and second parts served as input and output for the model during training. The first part of every gram is augmented with the destination cell of the trace where the gram comes from, and the second gram contains only the cell identifier of the next location (without timestamp).

Table 3.1 shows the descriptive statistics of the datasets.

3.4.3 Evaluation Metrics

Choosing a truly representative metric is always challenging and, to a large extent, application-dependent. We focused on some commonly used characteristics of PoIs, heatmaps, popular start and destination places, rush hours, traffic jams, trip lengths, etc. As a result, we consider four different utility metrics which are mainly borrowed from previous works [17, 42]. Each of them is evaluated both on the synthetic and the original dataset, and the difference is measured according to different distance metrics.

Trip size distribution

The Jensen-Shannon divergence (JSD) is computed between the distribution of the trip lengths in the synthetic and the original datasets in each hour of the day (the trip length is the number of cells of a trip). Note that, unlike the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence, JSD is symmetric and has a finite value. In our case, JSD is bounded between 0 (identical distributions) and 1 (least similar distributions).

Frequent patterns

The top- N most frequent patterns (i.e., subsequences of locations) are computed both in the original D and synthetic dataset D' , which are denoted by $F_N(D)$ and $F_N(D')$,

respectively. The true positive ratio $\frac{|F_N(D) \cap F_N(D')|}{N}$ is reported for $N = 10, 20, 50, 100$.

Spatio-temporal distribution of location visits

The spatio-temporal density in a given hour of the day is the number of visits in each cell of the considered region. This histogram, where each bin corresponds to a cell, is computed from both the synthetic and the original traces individually, and the spatio-temporal density of the original dataset as well as the synthetic datasets are obtained from these histograms after normalization. The Earth Mover’s Distance [64] is reported between these distributions, which measures their difference in terms of geographical distance (meters) and is a metric for probability distributions. Specifically, EMD measures the “amount of energy” (or cost) needed to transform one distribution to another where the ground distance is the geographical distance between the centers of cells. The EMD between the spatial densities of the original and synthetic data are reported for cells that include at least 80% of the data, but no more than 2000 cells for every hour, and also over all hours of the day.

Spatio-temporal distribution of source and destination pairs

The joint distribution of the source and destination locations is computed from the original and synthetic datasets individually, and their EMD is reported for every hour, and over all hours of the day. In particular, we count the relative frequency of every possible pair of source and destination locations in both datasets, and compute the EMD between these two distributions as above (the distance between a pair of location points is the sum of their individual distances). As the domain of this joint distribution has a size of $|\mathbf{L}| \times |\mathbf{L}|$ (in every hour, not over all hours), the computation of EMD can be very costly. We used the same approximation as for EMD density described above. Note that besides reporting the hourly EMD, we also calculated the EMD averaged over all hours in order to compare with prior works.

Route distribution

We calculate the histograms of cell visits for the inner points of a trace conditioned on the source and destination pairs, i.e. the histogram shows the distribution of cells that were visited between a given source and destination. The route distribution is calculated for both original and synthetic datasets, then their EMD is measured for each source-destination. Due to the high number of such pairs, we report the average of their EMD values. Intuitively, this metric measures how “realistic” a synthetic trace is. Due to

the very high number of source and destination pairs we used the same approximation described above.

3.4.4 Baselines

As comparison to DP-Loc, we evaluate the Ngram model from [17] (Ngram), and the AdaTrace model from [42]. We chose AdaTrace because it is the state-of-the-art technique and outperforms several other models (Ngram, DPT, SGLT) as stated in [42]. Ngram is chosen because it performs very well regarding frequent patterns and is a more general solution for any sequential data (unlike AdaTrace). For the reasons explained in Section 3.1, we do not compare DP-Loc to SGLT [11], since it is incompatible with the mobility patterns represented by our datasets. Moreover, our goal is to generate large synthetic datasets, and SGLT was shown [42] not to scale well in this regard⁶.

Since AdaTrace uses a dynamic grid configuration we had to align our grid in order to reach a fair comparison. First, we transformed the GPS coordinates with Mercator projection and applied all our preprocessing steps to the records (even top- K selection). Next, we generated synthetic traces with AdaTrace, where the output is also in the Cartesian space. For the evaluation with our metrics, we assigned the output coordinates to our non-dynamic grid cells.

As AdaTrace and Ngram apply the Laplace mechanism, for fair comparison, we changed it for the Gaussian mechanism and calculated the values of ϵ by the moments accountant method. For both models, given the value of $\delta = 1/|D|$ and $\epsilon = [0.5, 1, 2, 5]$, we analytically calculated the variance of the noise using Theorem 3.2.1. The L_2 sensitivity of the Adatrace can be shown to be $\Delta_2 = 1$ based on [42]. As for Ngram, we bounded the L_2 sensitivity with the L_1 for the same reason as in our top- K selection (see Section 3.3.3 for details).

3.4.5 Experiment setup

We experimentally evaluate the performance of our solution in terms of the above four utility metrics on the datasets described in Table 3.1. We also present the results of Ngram and AdaTrace on the same datasets, and compare these to our work using the four metrics. As neither Ngram nor AdaTrace releases time information, we dropped all timestamps in all datasets, and synthesized the resulting datasets with the two models (by contrast, DP-Loc was always executed on the original datasets with temporal information, and its results are reported in Figure 3.2 and 3.4). We obtained the implementation from

⁶We also tried to run DPT, but even for 100.000 traces it ran out of 100GB of memory.

the respective authors. Experiments were conducted using Tensorflow 2.0 and Python 3.6.9 on a single Linux server with 98GB RAM and 16 cores.

We have carried out our training in 24 different settings, combining $\epsilon = 0.5, 1, 2, 5$ with two grid resolutions (250 and 500), and three datasets (for statistics see Table 3.1). For the TI model, we set the L_2 -norm clipping threshold C_{TI} to 1.00, the batch size $|B|$ to 200, and ran the training over $e_{TI} = 15$ epochs (recall that $C_{TI}^2 \sigma_{TI}^2$ is the variance of the Gaussian noise added to the gradients in order to provide DP). With $\epsilon = 1$ and $\sigma_{TI} = 1.5$, the learning rate was set to 0.2; with $\epsilon = 2$ and $\sigma_{TI} = 1.00$, the learning rate was set to 0.5; and with $\epsilon = 5$ and $\sigma_{TI} = 0.7$, the learning rate was 0.5. Unless otherwise noted, we use $\delta = 1/|D|$ in the rest of the work, and ϵ is the overall privacy budget of DP-Loc. For the TPG model, we set the L_2 -norm clipping threshold $C_{TPG} = 3.0$, the batch size to 200, and trained the model over $e_{TPG} = 15$ epochs. With $\epsilon = 1$ and $\sigma_{TPG} = 1.6$, the learning rate was set to 0.1; with $\epsilon = 2$ and $\sigma_{TPG} = 1.00$, the learning rate was 0.15; and with $\epsilon = 5$ and $\sigma_{TPG} = 0.6$, the learning rate was 0.15. In dimensionality reduction, we add Gaussian noise to the counts of all location visits (when choosing the top- K locations, see Section 3.3.3) with $\epsilon = 1$, $\sigma_K = 3.8$; $\epsilon = 2$, $\sigma_K = 1.9$; and $\epsilon = 5$, $\sigma_K = 1.6$. The total ϵ of DP-Loc is computed according to Theorem 3.3.1 over 15 epochs for each of the TI and TPG models ($e_{TI} = e_{TPG} = 15$).

3.4.6 Results

In Figure 3.2 and 3.4, we report the hourly JSD and two EMD values between the original and the synthetic data generated by DP-Loc for $\epsilon = [0.5, 1, 2, 5]$. Figure 3.2 (and 3.4) show how the granularity of the grid influences the impact of the noise. Comparing the first and second lines of Figure 3.2 and 3.4, one can see that a larger grid size results in less error, though with coarsened data. (Coarsening the granularity eventually results in zero error of EMD, since all points end up in the same cell.) For comparison, we report the overall JSD, EMD-SD, EMD-Density and Frequent Patterns results of our synthetic traces and that of Ngram and AdaTrace in Table 3.5. GeoLife follows the same trends, thus we included the more comparative results in Table 3.5.

Trip sizes

In Figure 3.2 and 3.4, JSD shows the same trend and takes up very similar values for $\epsilon = 1, 2, 5$. However, this is not true for $\epsilon = 0.5$, since, to ensure such a low ϵ value, the algorithm requires considerably more noise. The San Francisco dataset shows the same tendency for JSD values (see 3.4). In the $\epsilon = 0.5$ case, JSD values are much larger when the cell size is 250m, also we can see that the EMD-SD values are also high. The TI

(a) JSD, cell size: 250 m

(b) JSD, cell size: 500 m

(c) EMD-SD (VAE), cell size: 250 m

(d) EMD-SD (VAE), cell size: 500 m

(e) EMD-Density, cell size: 250 m

(f) EMD-Density, cell size: 500 m

Figure 3.2: Performance of our approach on Porto dataset conditioned on time ($\delta = 4 \cdot 10^{-6}$).

(a) Distribution of start- destination heatmap on SF dataset, with 500m cells

(b) VAE generated distribution heatmap on SF dataset, with 500m cells and $\epsilon = 2$

(c) VAE generated distribution heatmap on SF dataset, with 500m cells and no DP

Figure 3.3: Comparison of the VAE generated distributions with the original source-destination distribution

model produced cells that were too close to each other, that caused very short traces (4.8 in average) in return. Table 3.5 shows that a larger grid generally results in larger JSD, but smaller EMD values for DP-Loc and AdaTrace, but larger for Ngram. *Recall that Ngram and AdaTrace do not include time information*, thus we only report one value for each setting in Table 3.5. To ease readability, we colored the best values at each metric among the three models in red. DP-Loc’s JSD results are clearly much lower (i.e., closer to the original distribution) than that of the other two models. The MH iterations and looping extension play a large part in these low results, but also by leaving out these steps we still get much lower JSD values than Ngram and AdaTrace (experiments show that such a JSD results in approximately a value of 0.5 JSD). Ngram generates traces without destination, and it does not select the globally most likely trace. In contrast to this, DP-Loc is more realistic. Although AdaTrace does include the destination, it still performs much worse than DP-Loc regarding trip sizes. We hypothesize that the high JSD values for AdaTrace could be due to the dynamic construction of the grid. AdaTrace works in two layers only and it is probable that many areas are not optimally divided, and our uniform grid with top-K selection performs better. Moreover, for Ngram and AdaTrace, the average generated trace length was approximately 3 (in all settings); both the mode and standard deviation were 2. In contrast to these, DP-Loc generates traces with an average length of 12, mode of 8 and standard deviation of 5, which are almost identical to the original statistics in Table 3.1.

Considering the algorithms of Ngram and AdaTrace, we can explain the large proportion of unrealistically short traces as follows. A trace of length 2 means that there is only the start and destination point in the trace, and with length three there is an intermediate point. Ngram represents the dataset with a prefix tree which contains the set of all grams occurring in the dataset along with their occurrence counts, i.e. Ngram adds noise to these counts and prunes the noisy tree by removing grams with too small noisy count in order to improve accuracy. which means that the random walk generated a terminal sign very early most of the time, thus the probability of termination is generally high for shorter grams. In particular, Ngram keeps grams only with sufficiently large occurrence counts, and shorter grams have larger counts which tend to survive sanitization unlike longer grams [17] with generally smaller counts. As a result, stronger privacy requirement (smaller ϵ) results in a set of shorter grams and eventually a smaller sanitized prefix tree. Although shorter sanitized grams can be combined into longer grams in Ngram, the number of possible extensions was not high in our datasets. The finally released grams coincide with the set of most frequently visited places and hence Ngram preserves the statistics of most frequent patterns accurately. The same holds for AdaTrace as well, because it also follows the Markov assumption to generate traces.

(a) JSD, cell size: 250 m

(b) JSD, cell size: 500 m

(c) EMD-SD (VAE), cell size: 250 m

(d) EMD-SD (VAE), cell size: 500 m

(e) EMD-Density, cell size: 250 m

(f) EMD-Density, cell size: 500 m

Figure 3.4: Performance of our approach on San Francisco dataset conditioned time ($\delta = 4 \cdot 10^{-6}$).

EMD source-destination

In Figure 3.2c, 3.2d, 3.4c and 3.4d, EMD is reported between the spatial distribution of the source and destination pairs depending on the time of the day. In Figure 3.2c

and 3.2d, EMD values stay steadily between 900 and 2000 meters except in Figure 3.2c, where the trend for $\epsilon = 0.5$ is similar but the values exceed 2500m. The results for the four different values of ϵ are almost the same if the larger cell size is used, and keep a steady distance in the 250m case. Furthermore, we present the heatmap of the generated distributions by our TI model in Figure 3.3 for the SF dataset where the cell size is 500m. We can see, that the model closely approximates the original distribution with $\epsilon = 2$. The goodness of the model is clearly represented in the third image, where we did not use differential privacy for the generation of source and destination points, it is almost exactly the same as the original distribution show in the first image. Table 3.5 shows that DP-Loc outperforms Ngram and AdaTrace, and generates more realistic endpoints for the traces. This demonstrates the generative power of the applied VAE network. The San Francisco dataset shows slightly different results. The EMD values in Figure 3.4 are almost the same for different values of ϵ , except for $\epsilon = 0.5$ in Figure 3.4c where EMD values are higher. We can also see that around 2 pm there is a peak in the two EMD values. We hypothesize that this is due to insufficient quality and quantity of data at that time period, which is not present in the Porto dataset. Nonetheless, DP-Loc still gives outstanding result in most cases. Note that smaller values are better, and EMD sums up all costs over the whole distribution. The distance between two neighboring cells is 250/500 m (center-to-center); if, e.g., EMD equals to 1000m, it is the size of 2/4 cells over the whole distribution.

EMD-Density

In Figure 3.2e, 3.2f, 3.4e and 3.4f, EMD is reported between the distribution of location visits for every hour of the day. Values show a trend similar to EMD-SD, but remain below 1000m in most cases, and $\approx 6 - 700$ m on average. The values for $\epsilon = 0.5$ again keep a distance from the other results with a peak just below 2000m for the smaller cell size. Ngram outperforms DP-Loc and Adatrace (except on Porto-500 where DP-Loc is the best). However, Ngram was originally designed to focus on the accurate release of the most frequent subsequences, and reconstructs traces from these. Therefore, as long as the number of visits per cell follows a power-law distribution, Ngram is expected to remain superior. Nevertheless, Table 3.5 also shows that DP-Loc significantly outperforms AdaTrace in all cases. Figure 3.5 shows the San Francisco heatmaps of the synthetic datasets generated by all three models compared to the original one in Figure 3.5a. Note that the scale of AdaTrace is lower than that of the rest (using the same scale would render AdaTrace’s patterns almost invisible). We can see that the original (left) image is more detailed than any other image, but DP-Loc and Ngram imitate it closely. The original image contains less highly populated areas (deep red), and Ngram has the densest cell of

Figure 3.5: Heatmaps of the synthetic and original databases.

all (ruby red) in downtown SF.

Frequent Patterns

Table 3.5 reports the overall results of the *Frequent Patterns* metric, that is, the true positive ratio of the top- N location subsets between the original and the private synthetic databases. For all datasets, DP-Loc and Ngram perform similarly; from all 120 cases DP-Loc outperforms Ngram 40 times, and underperforms 51 times, but in most cases the margin is very small. In all cases the performance of DP-Loc is higher than that of AdaTrace. The low FP values of DP-Loc regarding the GeoLife dataset show that the dataset size was insufficient for the neural networks to learn the underlying distribution. Beijing is approximately twice as big as Porto, however, the data available in the GeoLife dataset was only 1/8th of that. Comparing Figure 3.5 along with the FP results to the JSD results, we can see why there is not a single universal metric for fair comparison.

Ngram shows very good results when it comes to density (and frequent patterns), but the generated traces are highly unrealistic. DP-Loc might not perform as outstanding as Ngram regarding density metrics, but it produces realistic timestamped trajectories.

DP-Loc on smaller bounding-box

The San Francisco and Porto datasets contain the whole urban area with their airports included on the map. For fair comparison we have run DP-Loc on the downtown area of Porto, similarly to [42]. The results are shown in Table 3.2; we only evaluated the downtown area in one scenario where the cell size is $500m$ and $\epsilon = 1$. It is visible that the performance of AdaTrace is better than on a larger grid, however, the ratio among the best results is the same as measured with a larger bounding-box.

Dataset	FP-10	FP-20	FP-50	FP-100	JSD len	EMD-src-dst	EMD-Density
Ngram	0.90	0.90	0.84	0.98	0.878	1766	74
AdaTrace	0.40	0.50	0.64	0.58	0.709	1488	336
DP-Loc	0.90	0.85	0.95	0.90	0.278	1018	311

Table 3.2: Result measured on a downtown area in Porto. $\epsilon = 1$, and 10 Metropolis-Hastings iterations

Dataset	FP-10	FP-20	FP-50	FP-100	JSD len	avg len	std. dev. len	EMD SD	EMD dens.
SF-250	0.54	0.60	0.78	0.78	0.362	13	5.6	1572	602
SF-500	0.80	0.80	0.88	0.88	0.322	14	6.1	1669	629
Porto-250	0.70	0.90	0.90	0.92	0.296	13	5.3	1113	345
Porto-500	0.77	0.80	0.85	0.87	0.360	15	6.3	1201	367
GeoLife-250	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.408	10	3.0	4211	1201
GeoLife-500	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.480	10	3.5	4746	1116

Table 3.3: Result of our DP-Loc algorithm without Differential Privacy and with 10 Metropolis-Hastings iterations

DP-Loc without DP

We also evaluated DP-Loc without Differential Privacy, i.e. no noise was added to the model at any stage. Table 3.3 shows the results for the non-privacy preserving generated datasets. We can see that the numbers are almost identical to the ones in Table 3.5. The JSD and FP values are similar, and the two EMD values are lower than their private counterpart.

Justification for the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm

We applied the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm to the shortest paths in order to obtain convergence to a target stationary distribution over all paths, where the probability of a path is computed from the routing graph. In Table 3.4 we report the results of the route EMD metric, i.e., the EMD distance (in meters) between the original and the synthetic routes (cells) taken between source and destination pairs. Results show that for large datasets 10 iterations of MH results in the most realistic traces. However, for smaller dataset, where the added noise has a higher influence on the generated traces, 100 and 150 iterations of MH show sufficient improvement. Consequently, after 10 or 100 iterations we could also observe a small drop in the EMD-Density values as well.

	0	1	5	10	25	50	100	150
SF-500	1335	1252	1177	1154	1171	1177	1180	1179
Porto-500	1347	1229	1137	1116	1119	1126	1134	1135
GeoLife-500	1907	1693	1918	1794	1361	1150	1121	1119

Table 3.4: Results of route EMD for different Metropolis-Hastings iterations for $\epsilon = 1$ (measured in meters)

Trace Generation Complexity

We compute the number of generation steps of a single synthetic trace for each scheme as follows. Let us assume that all generative models are precalculated and saved. For a trace t with length $|t|$, DP-Loc takes $Z_{TI} + Z_{TPG}(K) + K^2 \log K + 2 \cdot |t|$ steps, where Z_{TI} and $Z_{TPG}(K)$ are the respective steps of the TI and TPG models, $K^2 \log K$ comes from Dijkstra’s algorithm, $2 \cdot |t|$ from the MH and looping parts of the model, and K is the number of top-K locations. As the graphs generated by TPI are precalculated, $Z_{TPG}(K)$ is ignored in the rest of the analysis. Since $|t| = O(K)$, the number of DP-Loc’s generative steps is dominated by Dijkstra’s algorithm, thus its complexity is $O(K^2 \log K)$.

AdaTrace’s generation steps depend on two random walks started from the start and destination points. The total number of generation steps accumulates into $2 \cdot m \cdot l$, where m is the size of the grid, and l is the maximal size of the generated trace (l is drawn from a distribution calculated from the original lengths). Since $l \leq m$, AdaTrace’s complexity is $O(m^2)$. If the grid is an order of magnitude larger than the number of top-K locations in DP-Loc, the empirical number of steps of AdaTrace can be larger than $K^2 \log K + Z_{TI} + 2 \cdot |t|$, e.g., $m = K^2$.

The expected number of steps in Ngram depends on the underlying data distribution. Evaluating Ngram on the taxi datasets, the average length of the generated traces are 3

steps only.

Experiments were conducted using Tensorflow 2.0 and Python 3.6.9 on a single Linux server with 98GB RAM and 16 cores. Running time is heavily dependent on the size of the input dataset. For the largest, the SF dataset the generation time for Ngram is on average 1 minute, for AdaTrace is 20s. In case of DP-Loc the trainings of the neural networks take up a lot of time. The overall running time of DP-Loc is approximately 3 hours. However, due to the fact that we are considering offline models, it only has to be done once.

3.5 Summary

Releasing location data is challenging owing to the fact that it is high-dimensional and sparse. We proposed a novel approach to release location data with strong privacy guarantees. In contrast to most prior works, DP-Loc is capable to release time information along with location visits without suffering significant utility loss. Our general framework consists of generating the source and destination pairs of every trace separately, computing the transition probabilities between neighboring locations, and then generating synthetic trajectories between the source and destination using a Monte Carlo algorithm. As opposed to previous works, the transition probability depends on the time and the destination towards where the individual is moving, and is computed only between the most frequent locations which make our solution accurate and scalable. We evaluated our proposal on two public location datasets and designed neural networks to model the distribution of trajectories. These networks are simple and hence fast to train even with DP guarantees. Our approach is evaluated on real-life location datasets of taxi passenger trajectories, and results show that the provided utility is meaningful. Therefore, our technique can be a compelling new approach to the privacy-preserving release of complete location trajectories with time information. Importantly, we produce synthetic datasets that preserve many different statistics of the original dataset. Undoubtedly, releasing only a few targeted statistics with or without Differential Privacy, instead of the complete synthesized dataset, is a different approach which should always result in greater accuracy but only with respect to the released statistics. There are several further research directions to explore. First, the proposed framework is general and finding the best generative models to a given type of data is difficult which requires domain expertise. Second, there can be several techniques to recover trajectories from the noisy transition probabilities which may provide superior performance to our trace generation. Finally, our general approach may be applicable to other types of sequential data than location trajectories such as different time series.

Table 3.5: Summary of results with 10 MH iterations. AdaTrace and Ngram ignores the time of trips, hence we report the overall JSD and EMD values over the whole period for our approach. Best values are in red.

		SF						Porto						GeoLife					
		250			500			250			500			250			500		
		Ngram	Ada	DP-Loc															
FP10	$\epsilon = 0.5$	0.80	0.20	0.80	0.90	0.20	0.80	0.80	0.20	0.70	0.90	0.28	0.60	0.66	0.05	0.30	0.70	0.01	0.70
	$\epsilon = 1$	0.80	0.10	0.80	0.90	0.10	0.82	0.80	0.20	0.65	0.90	0.30	0.70	0.70	0.05	0.30	0.80	0.05	0.60
	$\epsilon = 2$	0.80	0.20	0.85	1.00	0.30	0.85	0.80	0.10	1.00	0.90	0.40	0.70	0.80	0.10	0.28	0.80	0.14	0.87
	$\epsilon = 5$	0.80	0.10	0.85	1.00	0.40	0.90	0.90	0.10	1.00	0.90	0.40	0.70	0.90	0.16	0.30	0.92	0.20	1.00
FP20	$\epsilon = 0.5$	0.75	0.21	0.90	0.90	0.41	0.88	0.75	0.11	0.90	0.70	0.30	0.90	0.77	0.10	0.30	0.55	0.05	0.60
	$\epsilon = 1$	0.70	0.15	1.00	0.90	0.40	0.85	0.75	0.10	0.80	0.80	0.30	0.88	0.77	0.11	0.30	0.60	0.05	0.60
	$\epsilon = 2$	0.75	0.15	1.00	0.95	0.55	0.85	0.85	0.05	1.00	0.80	0.50	0.76	0.70	0.20	0.28	0.80	0.15	0.87
	$\epsilon = 5$	0.75	0.35	1.00	1.00	0.50	0.85	0.90	0.30	1.00	0.90	0.45	0.75	0.80	0.20	0.30	0.90	0.25	1.00
FP50	$\epsilon = 0.5$	0.95	0.18	1.00	0.80	0.60	1.00	0.90	0.15	0.90	0.80	0.45	1.00	0.80	0.10	0.25	0.58	0.12	0.53
	$\epsilon = 1$	1.00	0.12	1.00	0.80	0.60	1.00	0.95	0.14	0.90	0.80	0.42	0.93	0.80	0.10	0.28	0.58	0.12	0.40
	$\epsilon = 2$	1.00	0.34	1.00	0.84	0.62	0.95	0.95	0.26	1.00	0.90	0.40	0.88	0.85	0.16	0.28	0.80	0.27	0.87
	$\epsilon = 5$	0.91	0.36	1.00	0.86	0.62	0.92	1.00	0.26	1.00	0.80	0.42	1.00	0.80	0.29	0.30	1.00	0.27	1.00
FP100	$\epsilon = 0.5$	1.00	0.40	1.00	0.97	0.54	1.00	0.95	0.24	0.95	0.80	0.49	1.00	0.90	0.12	0.25	0.68	0.17	0.53
	$\epsilon = 1$	1.00	0.37	1.00	0.93	0.55	1.00	1.00	0.24	1.00	0.90	0.53	0.90	0.90	0.15	0.28	0.58	0.17	0.4
	$\epsilon = 2$	1.00	0.47	1.00	0.93	0.67	0.95	1.00	0.26	1.00	0.89	0.55	0.88	1.00	0.20	0.28	0.77	0.24	0.87
	$\epsilon = 5$	0.97	0.49	1.00	0.89	0.67	0.95	1.00	0.37	1.00	1.00	0.54	1.00	1.00	0.30	0.30	0.96	0.30	1.00
FP200	$\epsilon = 0.5$	1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	0.65	1.00	1.00	0.31	1.00	1.00	0.70	1.00	0.90	0.23	0.25	0.78	0.24	0.53
	$\epsilon = 1$	1.00	0.57	1.00	1.00	0.69	1.00	1.00	0.36	1.00	1.00	0.70	0.808	1.00	0.23	0.28	0.71	0.27	0.71
	$\epsilon = 2$	1.00	0.56	1.00	1.00	0.82	0.95	1.00	0.37	1.00	1.00	0.68	0.80	1.00	0.31	0.30	0.85	0.30	0.87
	$\epsilon = 5$	0.97	0.55	1.00	1.00	0.82	0.95	1.00	0.38	1.00	1.00	0.68	0.85	1.00	0.35	0.30	1.00	0.34	1.00
JSD length	$\epsilon = 0.5$	0.910	0.750	0.410	0.908	0.701	0.300	0.909	0.819	0.431	0.899	0.810	0.240	0.909	0.852	0.470	0.868	0.856	0.540
	$\epsilon = 1$	0.929	0.752	0.310	0.861	0.759	0.360	0.963	0.828	0.203	0.900	0.806	0.304	0.908	0.850	0.510	0.849	0.851	0.480
	$\epsilon = 2$	0.912	0.754	0.320	0.824	0.762	0.399	0.953	0.829	0.202	0.873	0.807	0.348	0.899	0.843	0.53	0.910	0.804	0.500
	$\epsilon = 5$	0.886	0.753	0.335	0.769	0.760	0.402	0.936	0.828	0.234	0.828	0.807	0.377	0.890	0.804	0.520	0.855	0.800	0.530
EMD src-dst (meters)	$\epsilon = 0.5$	2311	4002	2299	3356	2910	1771	2299	3002	1813	2999	2639	1389	5199	6988	5675	5799	8085	5760
	$\epsilon = 1$	2219	4112	1766	3438	2718	1682	2263	2995	1543	2923	2637	1259	5109	6509	5777	5652	7998	5638
	$\epsilon = 2$	2278	3166	1690	3470	1859	1673	2272	2874	1356	2899	2545	1284	4809	6444	4697	5032	7503	4769
	$\epsilon = 5$	2354	3127	1613	3137	1835	1499	2242	2885	1295	2801	2555	1219	4557	5985	4392	4841	7100	4588
EMD density (meters)	$\epsilon = 0.5$	199	1333	699	40	1303	1002	55	706	621	689	887	670	680	2003	2082	2174	2002	1990
	$\epsilon = 1$	154	1251	709	425	1308	808	46	783	650	480	769	429	405	1850	2081	2185	1999	1909
	$\epsilon = 2$	147	1087	797	471	1260	732	92	737	510	394	782	409	380	1300	987	1233	1677	1189
	$\epsilon = 5$	179	1083	741	451	734	788	135	1300	490	357	723	488	353	1114	1174	1150	1588	1290

Chapter 4

Conclusion and future work

In this dissertation we showed that driver re-identification is feasible in the presence of a realistic adversary. We presented two attacks on CAN bus data and proposed a differentially private generative model for location data. We can conclude that profiling drivers is feasible without appropriate anonymization techniques applied on either on these datasets (CAN or location). As we have seen, singling out of drivers based on their CAN logs can be performed even with or without reverse-engineering the CAN protocol depending on the strength of the adversary. First, we described a technique that automatically extracts the most descriptive signals from vehicles' CAN logs, consequently no manual extraction is needed. Aside from its privacy implications, the method for reverse engineering the CAN protocol can be of independent interest, thus, we hypothesize, that it could be applied for the reverse engineering of other proprietary protocols, such as those in (industrial) IoT. Second, further research showed that driver re-identification can be performed even without the nuisance of signal extraction or agreements with a manufacturer, meaning that a weaker attacker can also profile drivers using raw CAN logs. This implies that not revealing the exact signal location in CAN logs is not sufficient to provide any privacy guarantee in practice and that the *security by obscurity* approach what is widely applied by car manufacturers does not ensure strong security (or privacy) and can be easily broken. Our study does not only raise the flag to car drivers, but also to companies collecting in-vehicle network logs; the re-identification (and/or profiling) of drivers so effortlessly means that CAN logs indeed constitute personal data and, as such, are subject to the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [30]. Therefore it is a fundamental obligation of companies handling such data to adequately inform drivers and protect their personal data. It remains an open problem whether more sensitive attributes such as health status whose collection and processing require *explicit* consent of drivers [30], are also predictable from CAN logs.

Our work also advocates for the widespread adoption of standardized security proto-

cols for the protection of CAN network traffic [40]. Car companies should devise more principled (perhaps cryptographic) approaches to hide signals and/or to anonymize their CAN logs so that drivers cannot be re-identified. Although ad hoc solutions like dispersing the bits of a sensor signal within a CAN message would make both of the approaches (signal reverse engineering and driver re-identification without reverse engineering) less effective, it could also render the data useless. We conjecture that extracting signals from such obfuscated CAN messages remains feasible with appropriate statistical approaches. It also remains an open problem whether captured CAN logs can be effectively anonymized. Although car companies stress that the collected network logs are “anonymized”, the proper anonymization of such high-dimensional data is notoriously difficult in practice without significantly degrading accuracy [4]. We believe that most viable approaches include the release of aggregate noisy statistics with provable privacy guarantees [22].

In general, anonymizing large, sparse and high dimensional datasets is a hard problem, and it is not only CAN data that falls into this category. Location data also bears these characteristics, and organizations along with researchers are struggling to solve its anonymization problem. We proposed an approach to release location data with strong privacy guarantees. We believe this can aid organizations in developing practical tools to anonymize high dimensional datasets. This has particular importance in practice as an attacker can easily get access to location datasets which are bought and sold as commodity nowadays. In contrast to prior works on location data anonymization, our method is capable to release time information along with location visits without suffering significant utility loss. Compared to previous anonymization techniques, our method has strong privacy guarantees, and is scalable to large datasets. The proposed generative technique is simple and hence fast enough to train even with differential privacy guarantees. Results show that the provided utility is meaningful. Therefore, this technique can be a compelling new approach to the privacy-preserving release of complete location trajectories with time information. Importantly, the produced synthetic datasets preserve many different statistics of the original dataset.

Although the proposed framework is general, finding the best generative models to a given type of data is difficult and requires domain expertise. We believe that this general approach may be applicable to types of sequential data other than location trajectories such as different time series. However, this problem needs further investigation that we leave for future work.

Publications

Book Chapters

- [B1] ÁCS, G., LESTYÁN, SZ., BICZÓK, G., Privacy of Aggregated Mobility Data. In *Encyclopedia of Cryptography, Security and Privacy* (2021) pp. 1-5.

Conference and workshop papers

- [C1] REMELI, M., LESTYÁN, SZ., ÁCS, G., BICZÓK, G., Automatic driver identification from in-vehicle network logs. In *2019 IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (ITSC)* (2019)
- [C2] LESTYÁN, SZ., ÁCS, G., BICZÓK, G., AND SZALAY, ZS. Extracting vehicle sensor signals from CAN logs for driver re-identification. In *2019 13th 5th International Conference on Information Security and Privacy (ICISSP)* (2019)
- [C3] LESTYÁN, SZ. Secure Distributed Maximum and Maximal Clique Algorithms. In *2016 III. VOCAL Optimization Conference: Advanced Algorithms*. Esztergom, Hungary
- [C4] CSISZÁRIK, A., LESTYÁN, SZ., LUKÁCS, A. Efficient Apriori based algorithms for privacy preserving frequent itemset mining. In *2014 5th IEEE Conference on Cognitive Infocommunications (CogInfoCom)*. (2014) pp. 431-435

Journal papers

- [J1] LESTYÁN, SZ., ÁCS, G., BICZÓK, G., In Search of Lost Utility: Private Location Data. In *2022 Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETS)* (2022)
- [J2] LESTYÁN, SZ., Privacy Preserving Data Aggregation over Multi-hop Networks Networks. *Infocommunications Journal VIII/4*, (2016)

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